

A CONVERGENT - PARALLEL STUDY ON THE INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF BEED TEACHER EDUCATION STUDENTS

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A Convergent - Parallel Study on the Interpersonal Communication Skills of BEED Teacher Education Students

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Abstract

This study used mixed methods approach that examined the level of interpersonal communication skills. Thus, a convergent parallel mixed methods design was used since it is a type of design that could gather different but complementary data on the same topic. Random sampling was used to identify the 100 respondents for the quantitative phase and 14 for the qualitative: seven (7) for IDI and seven (7) for FGD were purposively selected. In the quantitative phase, the results of this study revealed that first year BEEed students oftentimes manifest their interpersonal skill through various aspects such as environment control, self- disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management, and immediacy. In qualitative phase, it was revealed that they were employing cross-cultural communication competence, embracing criticism or personal growth and professional development, encountering challenges in conveying messages in public speaking, and having disparities in communicating with varying individuals. Also, the students' insights shared were creating a positive and inclusive communication environment, seeking personal growth and self-development through interpersonal communication, cultivating interpersonal communication competencies, and applying holistic understanding through non-verbal cues. Data integration of both quantitative and qualitative data results indicated that there is convergence of findings from both types of data.

Keywords: *elementary education, interpersonal communication skills, mixed method study, Philippines*

Introduction

Interpersonal communication involves the exchange of ideas, information, feelings, and intention through messages and signals. Effective interpersonal communication skills are critical for personal and professional relationships, and they play an indispensable role in our daily lives. Interpersonal communication involves the exchange of ideas, information, feelings, and intention through messages and signals. This encompasses face-to-face interactions, where individuals rely on voice, facial expressions, body language, and gestures to convey their thoughts. However, studies about the interpersonal communication skills, specifically on the environmental control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management, and immediacy, of BEEed teacher education students are still unexplored (Sword, 2020; Ding, 2021).

In the global context, specifically in Yancheng Teachers University in China a counseling case highlighted the challenges faced by college students in interpersonal communication. While effective face-to-face communication is essential for building relationships, sharing information, and offering emotional support, students are increasingly dependent on mobile phones, making direct interaction difficult. This shift has brought attention to the psychological toll of poor interpersonal skills, with issues like anxiety and depression becoming more prevalent. The study emphasizes the need for interventions, such as cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), to help students improve communication skills, which are crucial for their mental health and academic success (Liu, 2019).

In the Philippines, a study was conducted about the issues and challenges that student teachers face. They found that the issues and challenges were largely related to classroom management, interpersonal communication skills, and instructional skills in their study. Their lack of strong communication skills hinders student teachers' ability to establish rapport, engage students meaningfully, and create a supportive learning environment. These difficulties in communication affect their capacity to address diverse student needs, foster a participatory classroom atmosphere, and manage classroom dynamics smoothly (Ganal, 2019).

In today's interconnected world, the increasing complexity of social interactions emphasizes the vital importance of effective interpersonal communication skills, making this a key area of social relevance. This study's exploration of enhancement programs aimed at boosting students' confidence in speaking and active listening is crucial, not only for personal and academic success but also for nurturing the social and emotional well-being of future leaders. This prompted me to conduct this study to provides insights for creating targeted interventions that empower students to excel academically and professionally. Prioritizing these skills fosters a generation that is academically competent, socially engaged, and emotionally resilient, thus supporting a more connected and empathetic society.

Additionally, in the literature reviews included in this study, there are related studies on the present study such as the study of Suprayogi (2019) entitled, "Emotional Intelligence and Interpersonal Communication Among Senior High Scholl Students". This study is correlational research which aims to examine the relationship between the emotional intelligence and interpersonal communication of senior high school students. Another study from Abid & Ali (2022) entitled, "Students' Interpersonal Skills and its Association with their Academic Achievement in Secondary School of Pakistan". This study showed importance of how interpersonal communication skills play in student's academic achievements. Last is study from Sebastianos (2023) entitled, "Integrating Project-Based Learning in Preparing Students' Interpersonal Communication Skills on Speaking Courses in Indonesia " which discussed about enhancing student's

interpersonal communication skills in high school context. These studies are in fact different from the present study given the fact that this research is conducted in the Philippines, is geographically localized, and primarily focuses on the BEED teacher education students in the Province of Davao del Norte utilizing a mixed methods research technique, it differs from previous studies.

The findings of the study will be widely disseminated to diverse research conferences and relevant agencies, aiming to foster scholarly exchange and facilitate the practical utilization of the research-based discoveries. This dissemination strategy seeks to actively contribute to the broader academic discourse and engage with organizations and entities directly involved or impacted by the study's outcomes. Additionally, providing copies to concerned agencies ensures that the research is accessible to those who can implement or benefit from its insights, thereby maximizing the real-world impact of the study's findings.

Research Questions

In this study, convergent parallel mixed method research was used in broadly examining the interpersonal communication skills of the 1st year BEED students in KCAST. Specifically, this sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of interpersonal communication skills of the 1st year BEED students?
2. What are the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of 1st year BEED students with regards to their interpersonal skills?
3. What are the insights of 1st year BEED students that they can share to their fellow students in general?
4. With the findings of the study, what intervention scheme can be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a mixed methods design, which involves integrating both qualitative and quantitative components within the research. Mixing in this context refers to the interconnection of qualitative and quantitative elements to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research issue. This integration is crucial at various stages of the research process to enhance the overall rigor of the study (Creswell & Plano, 2011).

In this study, this approach allowed for the integration of both qualitative and quantitative components to comprehensively investigate intercultural sensitivity among education students. By combining survey data with in-depth interviews, the study aimed to provide a nuanced understanding of how students perceive and navigate cultural diversity within educational settings. This integration throughout the research process was essential to ensuring a robust examination of intercultural interactions and attitudes among the study participants.

The convergent parallel mixed methods approach, as utilized in this study, is a non-experimental design that integrates both quantitative and qualitative components simultaneously. Creswell (2008) describes this approach as involving the concurrent collection and analysis of quantitative and qualitative data, with the results from both strands being compared or merged during the interpretation phase.

Further, a constructed survey questionnaire was given to 1st-year BEED students in KCAST as participants. There were 100 participants who replied to the research study. The consolidated answers of the participants gave numeric data about complications posed. Thus, appropriate statistical tools were utilized like frequency, weighted mean, and standard deviation. After undergoing this treatment, data was presented and analyzed using descriptive statistics.

On the other hand, in the qualitative phase of this study, the researcher used the phenomenological approach that reflected epistemological perspectives, believing that the validity of truth is multiple and subjective. Focus group discussions and one-on-one in-depth interviews were qualitative data collection methods effective in helping the researcher learn the social norms of a community, saturate the data collected from the in-depth interviews, and create themes based on the data collected by the researcher (Tripoli, 2014).

Thus, data were collected through focus group discussions and one-on-one in-depth interviews of the participants. The interview guide consisted of questions for the 7 chosen participants in one-on-one in-depth interviews and 7 participants for the focus group discussions. The questions were designed to elicit responses from the participants. The schedule of the interviews was set to facilitate the proceedings and to consider the availability of the participants. Every detail of the responses was taken into consideration, but those that were not relevant to the study were not reflected.

Participants

The participants of the study both in quantitative and qualitative strands are described in this section. The participants are essential in conducting this study as they are the primary sources of data needed in this study. With them, the goal of the study was achieved and realized.

Quantitative Phase

The respondents in the quantitative phase were the first-year elementary education students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology during the second semester of S.Y. 2023-2024. The study included a total of 126 respondents as the research samples, equally taken from first-year elementary education students. Additionally, in choosing and selecting the samples from the

given population of the study, stratified random sampling was used.

As explained by Simkus (2023), stratified random sampling is a method of selecting a sample in which a researcher first divides a population into smaller subgroups, or strata, based on shared characteristics of the members and then randomly selects among each stratum to form the final sample. In the study, the shared characteristics of the samples included their education level, degree or program, age, and gender.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Program</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
BEEd-Generalist	65	44	24%
BEEd-Generalist	65	44	24%
BEEd-Generalist	57	38	20%
Total	187	126	68%

Qualitative Phase

In qualitative research, subject selection was purposeful, employing the non-probability sampling technique known as purposive sampling. Participants were carefully chosen based on their ability to provide insightful responses that could inform the research questions and deepen the understanding of the studied phenomenon (Kuper et al., 2008). A total of 14 college students participated in this phase: seven for in-depth interviews and the remaining seven for focus group discussions. They volunteered to participate based on their interest and willingness to contribute to the study.

These students met specific inclusion criteria: (1) they were bona fide students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology, (2) they were enrolled in the teacher education program, and (3) they were first-year students. Students who did not meet these criteria or declined to participate voluntarily were excluded from the study.

Instrument

This study employed two methodological phases to the interpersonal communication skills of the students. The quantitative phase utilizes a modified questionnaire with a Five-point Likert Scale to measure dimensions such as interaction engagement and respect for cultural differences. Expert validation ensures the questionnaire's reliability. In the qualitative phase, a carefully crafted research guide elicits personal narratives and insights, supported by rigorous transcription verification.

Table 2. *Profiles of the Participants*

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-Level</i>
IDI-01	Male	1st Year
IDI-02	Female	1st Year
IDI-03	Male	1st Year
IDI-04	Male	1st Year
IDI-05	Female	1st Year
IDI-06	Female	1st Year
IDI-07	Male	1st Year
FGD-01	Male	1st Year
FGD-02	Female	1st Year
FGD-03	Female	1st Year
FGD-04	Male	1st Year
FGD-05	Female	1st Year
FGD-06	Female	1st Year
FGD-07	Male	1st Year

Together, these phases aim to comprehensively explore and understand the nuances of intercultural sensitivity among education students.

Quantitative Phase

The researcher employed a modified questionnaire for interpersonal communication skills, adapted from the work of Paes de Silva & Puggina (2014). This questionnaire employed a Five-point Likert Scale with indicators such as: environmental control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management and immediacy.

Within the Five-point Likert Scale, participants were instructed to rate and select a single box ranging from one (lowest) to five (highest) for each question. Notably, the Likert Scale has demonstrated efficacy in measuring constructs, attitudes, and stimuli that are not easily observable by human senses. Despite the adaptation of the questionnaire, a rigorous expert validation process was undertaken to ensure its reliability.

To gauge participants' perspectives on organizational commitment, the study provided a diverse range of means, descriptions, and interpretations for the collected data. This multifaceted approach aims to capture a comprehensive understanding of the participants' views on the topic.

Qualitative Phase

The panel of experts scrutinized the use of the qualitative research guide questionnaire to ensure its validity in terms of its clarity, suitability, understandability, and capacity to elicit personal narratives, comments, opinions, and insights from the research participants.

Additionally, the prepared open-ended questions were limited to three research issues and a maximum of five probing questions for each. Additionally, it offered crucial closing elements that ensured the participants' opportunity to make further comments. In order to make sure that the transcription of the data is accurate, the researcher also provided copies of the transcriptions to the concerned participants.

The objective also included reaching an agreement by comprehending various perspectives on the material.

Procedure

The procedure for gathering the data includes a number of steps. Quantitative and qualitative data were gathered concurrently, nearly at the same time. Parallel mixed-method data collection techniques were used to compare data from diverse sources, modify the data for comparison, or answer various types of inquiries (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2007).

Quantitative Phase

The researcher first requested permission from the Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology's office of the president to carry out this study in order to facilitate the collection of the required quantitative data. Additionally, the intercultural sensitivity survey questionnaire, which was developed, was used in this study to gather quantitative data. In order to prevent participant mood changes during the quantitative data collection, the survey questionnaire was given to participants on the same day.

Qualitative Phase

Focus group discussions and one-on-one in-depth interviews with participants were part of the qualitative data collection to obtain information about the participants' intercultural sensitivity. The researcher asked the informants about their time availability for the in-person interviews before starting the focus group discussions and one-on-one in-depth interviews. She also inquired about the preferred location of the interviews. The researcher used a planned set of enabling questions during the one-on-one in-depth interview and also provided follow-up questions to ensure that all of the subjects' answers was covered. The researcher went into great detail during the interview about the individuals' ethical concerns.

Data Analysis

Immediately after gathering all the pertinent data necessary, the tabulation and analysis of data was done after all pertinent data were collected. In analyzing the qualitative data, the researcher used thematic analyses. For the quantitative phase, certain statistical tools were used to analyze the data.

Quantitative Phase

In the analysis of quantitative data, descriptive statistics, such as the mean, was used to evaluate the average replies of the participants, and the dispersion was used to assess the variability of the respondents' responses on the survey's stress management questionnaire (Creswell & Creswell, 2017)

Qualitative Phase

In this phase, participants' responses were recorded, arranged, and reduced to themes through a process of coding and condensing the codes in qualitative data analysis. A narrative, a table, or a set of figures was used to present the data. The researcher totally immersed themselves in the rich, descriptive data during the analysis of the qualitative data, employing coding and categorization techniques to arrange the data. The objective was to create themes that may be utilized to describe the college students' level of intercultural sensitivity. Thus, qualitative analysis was an iterative process that involves generating and refining themes repeatedly as well as reading and rereading the data in order to get a final analysis of the data (Miles et al., 2014).

Ethical Considerations

The researcher was extremely cautious when conducting this study regarding ethical considerations. Permission was sought from school's president office to interview participants and deliver key study materials. Additionally, a consent letter was provided to the identified participants. The questions posed were clear and explicit, ensuring understanding among participants. Sensitivity was exercised in handling confidential material and delivering information amicably. Josselson (2007) emphasizes that narrative researchers have an ethical obligation to safeguard the privacy and dignity of individuals participating in the study. Therefore, the researcher exercised caution in presenting any unfavorable findings that are crucial to the welfare of the subjects. Ethical guidelines were strictly followed to uphold the rights and well-being of all participants involved in the research.

Social Value. This study aimed to clarify college students' interpersonal communication skills. To obtain a wide range of participant comments, which was the main goal of the analysis, the procedure for data collection was thoroughly explained. Presentations of the

study's findings were provided to both the participants and the general public. Additionally, the researcher adhered to the social value of research by openly dedicating to the accuracy of the convergent parallel mixed methods design employed in this study.

Informed Consent. An informed consent form was supplied to the study subjects. The permission provided details on the researcher's identity and affiliation, the purpose of the study, the length of the study, and any rewards provided to the subjects in the form of cash, gifts, or other objects in exchange for their participation. Due to the participants' privacy and secrecy, they were permitted to leave at any moment without giving a reason. The informed consent form (ICF) gave the participants the chance to read the information it contained, ask questions, and use their signature as an indication of their consent for the study.

Vulnerability of the Research Participants. The participants in this study were education students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology, and were not considered vulnerable. Nevertheless, each participant was treated with care and caution throughout the research process. Survey questionnaires were administered according to the participants' availability and preferred times, ensuring their convenience and comfort.

The Risks, Benefits and Safety. In this study, the number one concern was the safety and security of the participants, all of whom were of legal age. The conduct of the study was aligned with the participants' preferred places to gather the needed data to ensure their safety. Participants were given tokens of appreciation such as gifts, materials, or goods as a gesture of gratitude for helping the researcher conduct the study. Additionally, if participants experienced discomfort during the interview due to the sensitive nature of the subject being studied, the researcher provided them the option of not answering questions if they felt any psychological or emotional distress. Participants were also free to withdraw from the study if they were unable to discuss the requested data.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. Any data identified by the participants during this study was kept strictly confidential. Individual names were replaced with codes, and participants were given the option of not disclosing their names on the survey form when responding to the questionnaire. All responses were treated as confidential and stored by the researcher in a closed filing cabinet for three years. Names from all records were deleted to ensure anonymity, and there was no way to identify who completed the survey form. Hard copies of the data, containing only codes, were stored securely and protected.

Furthermore, Republic Act No. 10173, known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, protects individual personal information in information and communication systems in both the government and private sectors. Section 2 of the general provisions states the policy of the State to protect the fundamental human right of privacy of communication while ensuring the free flow of information to promote innovation and growth. The Act recognizes the importance of information and communications technology in nation-building and emphasizes the obligation to secure and protect personal information.

Any information that could potentially identify participants, such as gender, ethnicity, or employment/location description, was carefully phrased to avoid violating anonymity. Data collected was used solely for the purpose of the study and handled in accordance with ethical and legal standards outlined by the Data Privacy Act and other relevant regulations.

Justice. The study's participants were chosen for their appropriateness to the investigation. To avoid bias, the researcher adopted suitable sampling strategies for both the quantitative and qualitative phases. Participants were given the opportunity to read information and ask questions to understand their role in the study during the informed consent process. Participants were granted justice by contributing their time and knowledge to the completion of this study, and they received presents, goods, or anything else useful to their everyday lives as a token of appreciation. Justice was upheld by maintaining the confidentiality of the data obtained, accurately and appropriately transcribing the collected data, and sharing the findings with the participants first.

Transparency. This study adhered to the ideals of transparency by fully informing the participants that the study focused on the level of interpersonal communication skills of education students in terms of gender equality. The researcher took responsibility to conduct the study with fairness and justice. Additionally, participants were presented with interview notes and transcribed documents for confirmation and approval. Therefore, the results of the study were shared with the respondents and participants.

Qualification of the Researchers. The researcher was reliable and credible while conducting this study, which focused on the interpersonal communication skills among education students. The researcher was a third-year college student pursuing a Bachelor of Elementary Education-Generalist program, conducting this study to enhance personal knowledge and contribute to research development.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher ensured that existing and available resources needed for this institutional study were accessible. Online journals, periodicals, magazines, books, and unpublished dissertations were utilized to gain further understanding and references, providing various literature and readings that supported the variables used in the study. Adequate facilities, such as a laptop and cellphone, were provided to ensure the accuracy of collecting data from the participants during the study.

Community Involvement. During the initial presentation of this study, community leaders, faculty, and students were invited to the public forum, which was conducted through virtual meetings and presentations. This research aimed to generate awareness, and implications were provided to school administrators and instructors regarding the survey of intercultural sensitivity among education students. The study was beneficial for the technical research committee, conference managers, and journal publishers who assisted in disseminating the results to provide additional information and a deeper understanding of intercultural sensitivity among education

students.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of data in both quantitative and qualitative phases. The first phase deals with the quantitative part in which it shows the level of interpersonal communication skills of elementary education students in terms of environment control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management, and immediacy. The second phase focuses on the qualitative portion, where it presents the lived experiences, coping mechanism, and insights of elementary education students when it comes to their interpersonal communication skills. Also, the matrix contains the issues probed, core ideas, codes or categories, essential themes, and the supporting theoretical perspectives. Further, another matrix shows the data integration of the salient quantitative and qualitative findings.

Level of Intrapersonal Communication Skills

Interpersonal Communication Skills. Table 2 presents the level of interpersonal communication skills of elementary education students in Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. It obtained a mean score of 3.44 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Environment Control. The results indicated a moderate level of environment control, with a mean of 3.37 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicated that it is sometimes manifested by elementary education students. The highest mean is item No.1 Finding easily the right words to express myself obtaining a mean score of 3.68 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This result indicated that it is always manifested by the elementary education students. In contrast, item No.3 Persuading others to my position got the lowest mean of 3.03 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. It indicates that it is sometimes manifested by the elementary education students.

Table 2. *Level of Intrapersonal Communication Skills*

No.	Items	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Environment Control			
1	Finding easily the right words to express myself	3.68	High
2	Accomplishing my communication goals.	3.47	High
3	Persuading others to my position.	3.03	Moderate
4	Excelling in expressing myself verbally.	3.18	Moderate
5	Characterizing my conversation to a smooth shift from one topic to next.	3.47	High
	Category Mean	3.37	Moderate
Self-Disclosure			
1	Describing myself as being nice to everyone.	3.50	High
2	Revealing how I feel to others.	3.03	Moderate
3	Telling people when I feel close to them.	3.47	High
4	Letting people think that I understand them.	3.47	High
5	Letting people know what I'm thinking.	2.92	Moderate
	Category Mean	3.28	Moderate
Assertiveness			
1	Going to confront the person who has wronged to me.	2.92	Moderate
2	Taking charge of conversation I'm in by negotiating what topics we talk about.	3.13	Moderate
3	Having trouble in standing up myself.	3.45	High
4	Standing up for my rights.	3.87	High
5	Communicating others as though they're equal.	3.71	High
	Category Mean	3.42	High
Interaction Management			
1	Letting others know that I understand what they are saying.	3.68	High
2	Perceiving not only what they say but also what they do not say.	3.39	High
3	Feeling comfortable in social situation	3.16	Moderate
4	Making sure that my communication is usually descriptive not evaluative.	3.21	Moderate
5	Making myself a good friend to my friends.	4.05	High
	Category Mean	3.50	High
Immediacy			
1	Allowing my friends to see who really I am.	3.89	High
2	Making sure that my friends truly believe that I care about them.	3.87	High
3	Trying to look in the eyes when I speak to them.	3.74	High
4	Letting my friends to tell me I'm happy or sad.	3.21	Moderate
5	Putting myself to other's shoe.	3.53	High
	Category Mean	3.65	High
	Overall	3.44	High

Self-disclosure. It is also shown on the table that the average score for level of intrapersonal communication skills in terms of self-disclosure obtained an average score of 3.28 with descriptive equivalent of moderate. This means that it is sometimes manifested by

elementary education students. As shown on the table, item No.1 Describing myself as being nice to everyone obtained the highest mean of 3.50, indicating a descriptive equivalent of high, which means that it is oftentimes manifested among elementary education students. On the other hand, the lowest mean is item No.5 Letting people know what I’m thinking obtaining a mean score of 2.92 with a description equivalent of moderate. This just indicates that it is sometimes manifested by elementary education students.

Assertiveness. The level of interpersonal communication skills in terms of assertiveness obtain an overall mean of 3.42 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that it is oftentimes manifested by the elementary education students. As shown in the table, item No.4 Standing up for my rights, got the highest rating, which obtained a mean score of 3.87 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that it is oftentimes manifested among elementary education students. In contrast, the lowest mean is item No.1 Going to confront the person who has wronged to me with a mean score of 2.92 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate, which means that it is sometimes manifested.

Interaction Management. The level of interpersonal communication skills in interaction management is oftentimes manifested by elementary education students with an overall mean of 3.50 with a descriptive equivalent of high. As shown in the table, item No.5 Making myself a good friend to my friends, got the highest mean of 4.05 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that it is oftentimes manifested by the elementary education students. On the other hand, the item No.3 Feeling comfortable in social situation received the lowest mean score among the indicators, with a mean score of 3.16 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This result indicates that it is sometimes manifested.

Immediacy. The interpersonal communication skills in terms of immediacy obtained a mean of 3.65 with a description of high. This indicates that it is oftentimes manifested by elementary education students. As shown on the table, for this indicator, item No.1 Allowing my friends to see who really I am is oftentimes manifested by elementary education students with the highest mean score of 3.89 with a descriptive equivalent of high. In contrast to that, the lowest mean in this indicator is item No.4 Letting my friends to tell I’m happy or sad with a mean of 3.21 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that it is sometimes manifested by elementary education students.

Lived Experiences and Coping Mechanisms with Regards to Their Interpersonal Skills

There were four essential themes drawn from the responses of the participants of the in-depth interview and focus group discussion. These are employing cross-cultural communication competence, embracing criticism or personal growth and professional development, encountering challenges in conveying messages in public speaking, and having disparities in communicating with varying individuals.

Table 3. Lived Experiences and Coping Mechanisms of BEED Students with Regards to Their Interpersonal Skills

Issues Probed	Core Ideas	Code/ Categories	Essential Themes	Theoretical Support
Strategies for effective cross-cultural communication	Understanding cultural contexts and showing respect for diverse cultures Adapting communication styles to diverse cultural contexts Employing strategies for effective cross-cultural communication Flexibility in communication styles to align with cultural norms. Adopting active listening to avoid misunderstand-dings when communicating. Flexibility in modifying communication styles based on specific contexts.	Minding other person’s culture Having flexible communication methods	Employing Cross-Cultural Communication Competence	Hofstede’s Cultural Dimensions Theory
Effective Handling of criticisms and feedbacks in communication	Importance to acknowledge people’s feelings and feedback Adapting criticism and feedback from others to improve communication skills. Adjusting oneself and using criticism in expressing thoughts as motivation to improve and disseminate information effectively. Viewing criticism and feedback as an opportunity for self-improvement and growth. Remaining calm and responding constructively when facing criticism or feedback. Responding to criticism depending on the situation. Listening actively and understanding feedback when dealing with criticism.	Seeing Criticisms for improvement Receptiveness to Constructive Feedback	Embracing Criticism or Personal Growth and Professional Development	Erikson’s Psychosocial Development Theory
Role of effective	Challenges in effectively delivering ideas	Failing to	Encountering	Communication

interpersonal communication skills in enhancing academic engagement and collaboration.	fluently. Troubles in constructing ideas due to fear of embarrassment in participating. Having a low voice volume and other difficulties in effective communication. Facing difficulties in disseminating information and expressing oneself. Challenges in effective classroom communication arise from lack of confidence and listening skills. Lack of confidence in speaking and constructing ideas hindering effective interpersonal communication. Fear of public speaking and making mistakes in front of others hindering effective communication and participation.	effectively convey ideas Being anxious when talking in front of many people Lack of Confidence when speaking in public	Challenges in Conveying Messages in Public Speaking	Apprehension Theory
Impact of interpersonal communication on student-teacher relationships and the use of formal language in professional contexts.	Ability to communicate with peers due to mutual understanding. Ability to effectively express oneself and be understood Confidence in expressing ideas to peers and building relationships through effective communication. Existence of barriers in communicating due to the need for formality when interacting with professionals. Perceiving one's ability to communicate with teachers as not very good. The need to use of a formal context when communicating with professionals.	Being able to express and communicating effectively to peers Employing formal communication methods when communicating with professionals	Having Disparities in Communicating with Varying Individuals	Communication Accommodation Theory

Employing Cross-Cultural Communication Competence. The experiences derived from interviews and focus group discussions reveal that elementary education students are actively developing cross-cultural communication competence. These students demonstrate a keen awareness of the importance of minding other persons' cultures and exhibit flexibility in their communication methods. They recognize and respect cultural differences, adjusting their language choices and nonverbal cues to be inclusive and culturally appropriate. Furthermore, they show a willingness to learn about and adapt to diverse cultural backgrounds, enhancing their ability to build meaningful and respectful relationships with peers from various cultural contexts.

Minding Other Person's Culture. As a key lived experience and coping mechanism, participants emphasized the importance of minding other persons' cultures in their interactions. Through interviews and focus group discussions, they shared how they attentively consider cultural nuances and adapt their communication styles to respect diverse backgrounds. This cultural mindfulness not only helps them navigate intercultural interactions more effectively but also fosters a deeper sense of empathy and cooperation.

Participants emphasize the importance of understanding different cultures as a fundamental aspect of effective communication. They acknowledge that cultural awareness goes beyond language proficiency. This understanding helps individuals navigate conversations with greater sensitivity, preventing potential conflicts or misinterpretations that might arise from cultural differences. As one of the Participant shared:

“In my perspective it is important to have an understanding to such culture or context to some people to have a good flow of communication, my coping strategies for this is to ask question and showing respect to other culture.” (IDI-07)

(In my perspective it is important to have an understanding to such culture or context to some people to have a good flow of communication, my coping strategies for this is to ask question and showing respect to other culture.)

Furthermore, elementary education students highlight the critical need to adapt their communication styles to diverse cultural and social contexts, fostering a deeper sense of cultural sensitivity. This approach requires not only an awareness of others' cultural backgrounds, values, and communication norms but also a commitment to engaging in effective and respectful interactions. As one of the Participant stated:

“So for me, I adopt the communication style in diverse cultural or social context in a way that being cultural sensitive, una dapat makabalo ta kung unsa ang mga different culture jud sa mga tao since, we are diverse dapat makabalo ta sa ilahang cultural background sa ilahang values and sa ilang communication norms para ma aware ta kung unsa ang atung dapat icomunicate ug maging careful jud ta sa mga words nga atung iingon sa ilaha . sa kana na paagi, maka show tag respect for cultural diffrences.” (FGD-01)

(So for me, I adopt the communication style in diverse cultural or social contexts in a way that is culturally sensitive. We should know

about the different cultures of people since we are diverse. We need to understand their cultural backgrounds, values, and communication norms to be aware of what we should communicate and be careful with the words we say to them. In this way, we can show respect for cultural differences.)

Moreover, participants develop and employ respectful and flexible communication strategies to ensure successful interactions across different cultural contexts. They recognize that effective communication requires more than just understanding the language; it also demands an awareness of cultural subtleties and sensitivity to contextual factors. As one of the Participant indicated:

“My strategy involved is using inclusive language avoiding assumption and adjusting tone and vocabulary based on the situation. Additionally, I prioritize active listening and seeking clarification when needed to insure effective communication across diverse background.” (FGD-02)

(My strategy involved is using inclusive language avoiding assumption and adjusting tone and vocabulary based on the situation. Additionally, I prioritize active listening and seeking clarification when needed to insure effective communication across diverse background.)

Having Flexible Communication Methods. In the interview, participants highlighted the importance of having flexible communication methods in their interactions. Through interviews and focus group discussions, they shared how they adapt their communication styles to suit various cultural contexts, ensuring effective and respectful exchanges. This flexibility includes modifying their language, tone, and nonverbal cues to align with the cultural expectations of their peers.

Participants underscore the critical role of flexibility in communication as a coping strategy, enabling them to navigate varying behaviors and attitudes across different cultural contexts. They emphasize that being adaptable in communication is essential for successfully interacting with individuals from diverse backgrounds. his adaptability extends to both verbal and non-verbal communication, requiring them to adjust not only their language but also their body language to fit the cultural expectations of those they are engaging with. As expressed by one of the Participant:

“So for me maam, lahi-lahi man ang behavior ug attitude sa mga tao ang unang coping strategies nko maam is dapat flexible ka on how you communicate because it allows you to adapt to different cultures, context and this might include adjusting your language or body language to be more in line with the cultural norms of the person or group you communicating with.” (IDI-02)

(So for me, ma'am, since people have different behaviors and attitudes, my first coping strategy is to be flexible in how you communicate because it allows you to adapt to different cultures and contexts. This might include adjusting your language or body language to align more with the cultural norms of the person or group you are communicating with.)

Additionally, participants underscore the importance of active listening, respect, and sensitivity in adopting communication styles across diverse cultural or social contexts. They emphasize flexibility and the willingness to ask questions or seek clarification when uncertain about cultural practices or norms, aiming to foster mutual understanding. As Participant 6 highlighted:

“I adopt the communication of diverse cultural of social context by active listening of course pag respect and sensitivity, flexibility and of course mag ask ug question or clarification when dili sure about a certain cultural practices or norms. I act polite to avoid misunderstanding.” (IDI-6)

(I adopt the communication of diverse cultural of social context by active listening of course respect and sensitivity, flexibility and of course asking question or clarification when unsure about a certain cultural practices or norms. I act polite to avoid misunderstanding.)

Furthermore, participants stress the significance of flexibility as a key strategy in adapting communication styles to diverse cultural or social contexts. By modifying their approach based on the specific cultural or social nuances of each conversation, individuals aim to ensure effective and respectful communication. Participant 13 articulates this approach:

“The strategy that I am going to used is being flexible or flexibility. It can modify communication style based on specific cultural or social context for the conversation. So, mao ni akong coping mechanism to ensure that my communication remains effective ug respectful across diverse cultural and social studies.” (FGD-6)

(The strategy that I am going to use is flexibility. It allows me to adjust my communication style based on the specific cultural or social context of the conversation. This is my coping mechanism to ensure that my communication remains effective and respectful across diverse cultural and social settings.)

Embracing Criticism or Personal Growth and Professional Development. In exploring the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of elementary education students, a prevalent theme emerges: the embracement of criticism as a catalyst for personal and professional development. Participants demonstrate a receptiveness to constructive feedback, viewing criticism as an opportunity for improvement rather than a setback. They exhibit a keen understanding of the value of constructive criticism in refining their skills and practices, actively seeking opportunities for growth and self-improvement.

Seeing Criticisms for Improvement. Elementary education students, when discussing their communication experiences, emphasize the importance of viewing criticisms as opportunities for growth and development. They articulate specific strategies for incorporating

constructive feedback into their communication practices, highlighting their commitment to continuous improvement. This underscores their proactive stance towards refining their skills and practices, indicative of a growth-oriented mindset.

Participants stress the importance of feedback in communication, emphasizing its dual role in expressing emotions and driving personal improvement. They view feedback as an essential element for growth, demonstrating a proactive approach in embracing both positive and negative critiques. Rather than reacting defensively to criticism, they see it as an opportunity for learning and self-improvement. As one of the Participant articulates this approach:

“...tanan tao is ahmm.. sap ag communicate is naa juy feelings and it is important that kanang naa silay maingon saako na dili maayu na feedback so akong buhaton is dili lang nko I adapt katung gipang ingon nila saako nga dautan and kung naa may mga feedback na maayu saako, so ako syang I adapt and by that so maka learn ko sailaha but naa pud koy kamalian pud and by that maimprove akaong pagiging ahh.. facing sa mga tao and ma correct nako akong mga bad doing.” (IDI-01)

(Everyone has feelings when communicating, and it is important when someone gives me negative feedback. What I do is not simply adapt to the bad things they say about me, but if there is positive feedback, I take it and adapt to it. By doing this, I learn from them. I also recognize that I have my own mistakes, and through this, I can improve how I interact with people and correct my wrongdoings.)

Additionally, participants emphasized the inevitability of receiving criticism, acknowledging that it can be both positive and negative. They recognized that feedback, especially from teachers, plays a crucial role in enhancing their communication skills, particularly when it comes to improving their speaking pace and delivery during presentations. As one of the Participant illustrates this perspective:

“Dili man malikayan na e criticize ka sa isa ka tao, it’s either good or bad and ilang feedback saimoha. Para saakoa maam inig mag report ko and comment jud sa mga teachers saako kay hinay akong tingog, paspas ko mag report tas mailhan nil ana nakulbaan ko I adapt nako to ilang feedback as good maam pra inig sunof report nako maam dili nako hinay ug tingog, paspas mo report ug masabtan pud ko sa mga learners maam.” (IDI-02)

(It is unavoidable to be criticized by others, whether the feedback is good or bad. For me, when I report and teachers comment that my voice is soft, that I speak too fast, and they can tell that I am nervous, I take their feedback positively. So, for my next report, I will not speak softly or too quickly, and the learners will be able to understand me better, ma'am.)

Furthermore, participants highlight the significance of adapting communication styles to diverse cultural or social contexts. They stress the importance of active listening, respect, and sensitivity in fostering mutual understanding. The participant highlights how receiving criticism, particularly in academic settings, serves as a tool for self-improvement. As one of the Participant articulates this approach:

“...akoa lang gyud I adjust or ang akoang self na kanang kuan dili lang pud maka ko makasamok. In terms og kuan sa academi nako kanang ma criticize bitaw ko sa during report ana then nay times nga dili ko ka express og maayu sa thoughts usahay ma criticize ko sa maistra ug mga classmates kay dili nako matarung og disseminate ang information so kanang mga criticism is gina buhat nako na motivation aron ma improve pa gyud bitaw akong self.” (IDI-03)

(I just really adjust myself so that I do not cause any trouble. In terms of my academics, when I get criticized during a report and there are times when I cannot express my thoughts well, I get criticized by the teacher and classmates because I cannot properly disseminate the information. I use those criticisms as motivation to further improve myself.)

Moreover, elementary education students emphasizes the value of embracing criticism and feedback as opportunities for growth and self-improvement. By acknowledging the positive aspects of judgments from others, individuals can utilize these insights as a means to identify areas for personal development and strive for continuous betterment. As one of the stated by Participant:

“Facing the criticism of feedback from someone is going to challenging however, when receiving judgments from others I think I can see these both like a positive side as through judgements we can use this as an opportunity or a door to seek improvements on what is lacking towards ourselves on how we make things to improve for the better.” (FGD-05)

(Facing the criticism of feedback from someone is going to challenging however, when receiving judgments from others, I can see these, both like a positive side as through judgements. We can use this as an opportunity or a door to seek improvements on what is lacking towards ourselves on how we make things to improve for the better.)

Receptiveness to Constructive Feedback. In the interviews conducted with elementary education students, a recurring theme emerges: a strong inclination towards being receptive to constructive feedback. Participants express a willingness to actively seek and embrace feedback as a means of enhancing their communication skills. This receptiveness demonstrates their commitment to personal and professional growth, as they recognize the value of constructive criticism in refining their abilities and fostering continuous improvement.

Participants emphasizes the significance of maintaining composure when confronted with criticism or feedback. By prioritizing emotional regulation and taking a pause to collect thoughts, individuals can respond constructively rather than react defensively. This approach fosters effective communication and allows for meaningful dialogue aimed at addressing concerns and facilitating growth. As one of the Participant aptly articulates:

“When facing criticism or feedback from someone, I try magpabilin nga kalmado. Of course it important not to let my emotion takeover. I take a moment nga muginhawa and collect my thought before responding and respond constructively instead our reality defensively and I respond in a constructive manner.” (IDI-06)

(When facing criticism or feedback from someone, I try to remain calm. Of course it important not to let my emotion takeover. I take a moment to breath and collect my thought before responding and respond constructively instead our reality defensively and I respond in a constructive manner.)

Moreover, elementary education students also highlighted the nuanced approach to receiving criticism, emphasizing the importance of considering the context of the situation. They acknowledge the need to address offensive criticism assertively while also valuing constructive feedback that aids in personal improvement. This perspective underscores the significance of effective communication, where both parties engage respectfully to facilitate growth and understanding. As one of the Participant conveyed:

“...it depends of the situation, if iyahang gicriticize sa akoa is murag offensive na in that way kailangan kong muingon sa iyaha nga dapat kung muhatag kag criticism sa isa ka tao dapat in a proper pud siya nga mutingog pud ko sa akong side pero if iyahang feedback sa akoa is makahatag og improvement sa akoa nga makaanalayze pud ko atleast maimproved akoang communication skills na magrespect ug respond appropriately ko sa iyaha.”(FGD-01)

(It depends on the situation. If someone gives me criticism, but it is offensive, then I need to tell them that when giving criticism, they should do it properly. I also need to speak up for myself. However, if their feedback helps me improve, I can analyze it and think, 'Ah, okay,' and it helps improve my communication skills to respect and respond appropriately to them.)

In addition, participants emphasize the importance of effectively managing criticism by highlighting the role of active listening and the ability to separate feedback from personal identity. They believe that by concentrating on the actions or behaviors being critiqued rather than viewing the feedback as a judgment of their character, individuals can cultivate a more constructive mindset. As one of the Participant elucidates this perspective:

“I believed when dili with criticism is important to listen carefully actively to understand the feedback and also separate the criticism from your personal identity, it’s all about your actions, not you as a person. and important thing we should focus on the constructive aspects of the criticism and how you can learn from it.” (FGD-05)

(I believe that when dealing with criticism, it is important to listen carefully and actively to understand the feedback. Also, separate the criticism from your personal identity; it is about your actions, not you as a person. It is important to focus on the constructive aspects of the criticism and how you can learn from it.)

Encountering Challenges in Conveying Messages in Public Speaking. The experiences of elementary education students shed light on the hurdles they face in effectively communicating ideas in public speaking engagements. Many express feelings of anxiety and a lack of confidence when addressing large audiences, which often leads to difficulties in conveying messages with clarity and impact. Despite their passion for communication, these challenges present formidable obstacles that require resilience and skill-building to overcome.

Failing to Effectively Convey Ideas. Within the narratives of elementary education students, the challenge of failing to effectively convey ideas emerges as a significant hurdle in their communication journey. Participants candidly express frustrations stemming from instances where their intended messages fail to resonate or are misunderstood by their audience. This struggle underscores the complexities of communication and highlights the need for ongoing skill development and self-reflection.

Participants reflect on the challenges they face in effectively expressing their ideas, often stemming from difficulties in delivering fluent speech. These moments of struggle can be frustrating, as individuals may feel that their thoughts are not coming across clearly or coherently. However, rather than viewing these challenges as setbacks, participants see them as valuable opportunities for personal growth. This perspective encourages them to confront their fears of public speaking and engaging with others. As expressed by a Participant:

“...kanang dili kaayu ko as in fluent sap ag deliver sa akong mga ideas because naa mangud instances na ahh akong gipasabot is wala syay kabuluhan dili sya connected so those challenges is... naga push saakoa to face people.” (IDI-01)

(I am not very fluent in delivering my ideas because there are instances where what I am trying to convey seems meaningless or not connected. These challenges push me to face people.)

Furthermore, elementary education students commonly encounter challenges in engaging in effective interpersonal communication in the classroom, particularly related to constructing ideas and pronunciation. These challenges often lead to feelings of apprehension about participating in class discussions for fear of making pronunciation errors and feeling embarrassed. As highlighted by one of the Participant:

“The challenges that I face in engaging effective interpersonal communication in the classroom is constructing my ideas and my pronunciation, kini ang kasagaran jud na challenges na akong ginabase karun kay tungod ani maulaw ko magparticipate sa classroom kay basin mamali ko sa akong pronunciation og maulawan rako.” (FGD-02)

(The challenges that I face in engaging in effective interpersonal communication in the classroom are constructing my ideas and my pronunciation. These are the usual challenges I face now. Because of this, I am embarrassed to participate in the classroom as I might mispronounce words and end up feeling humiliated.)

Being Anxious When Talking in Front of Many People. Among the elementary education students, a prevalent challenge arises in the form of anxiety when speaking before large audiences. Participants candidly share feelings of nervousness and apprehension, which often hinder their ability to communicate effectively. This anxiety underscores the psychological complexities associated with public speaking and highlights the importance of implementing coping mechanisms and seeking support to manage these feelings.

Participants frequently share their personal experiences regarding the challenges they encounter during presentations, highlighting common issues such as speaking softly, delivering reports too hastily, or grappling with nervousness. These experiences shed light on the real-time struggles that individuals face in public speaking scenarios, emphasizing the emotional and psychological factors at play when presenting in front of an audience. As one of the Participant exemplifies this sentiment:

“Sa akong na mention maam when it comes saakong presentation hinay akong tingog, tapos pas-pas ko mag report, tapos mailaw ko. Mao jud na akong mg ana experience maam.” (IDI-02)

(The challenges that I face in engaging in effective interpersonal communication in the classroom are constructing my ideas and my pronunciation. These are the usual challenges I face now. Because of this, I am embarrassed to participate in the classroom as I might mispronounce words and end up feeling humiliated.)

Also, elementary education students often encounter challenges in effectively disseminating information or expressing themselves in front of the classroom, particularly during reports or oral recitations. These challenges may stem from difficulty in articulating thoughts coherently or maintaining clarity in communication, leading to frustration. As one of the Participant reflects on such difficulties:

“...maglisod ko ug disseminate ang mga information or mag express saakong self in front the classroom the kanang mag report ko or mag answer sa mga orasl recitation kay naa may usahay na kanang akoang thoughts kay kanang tarung sya saakong huna-huna pero inig isulti na nako mabali or matuyok tuyok akong ideas. Then dili ko ka effectively communicate. Mao na isa sa mga challenges nga akoang na experience.” (IDI-03)

(I have difficulty disseminating information or expressing myself in front of the classroom when I report or answer during oral recitation. Sometimes my thoughts are clear in my mind, but when I speak, they get mixed up or jumbled. As a result, I cannot communicate effectively. This is one of the challenges I experience.)

Lack Of Confidence When Speaking in Public. Elementary education students articulate a common struggle with a lack of confidence when speaking in public settings. Participants candidly express how this lack of confidence undermines their ability to communicate effectively and convey their ideas with conviction. This challenge highlights the psychological barriers that can impede effective communication, necessitating strategies for building self-assurance and assertiveness.

Elementary education students frequently identify a lack of confidence and inadequate listening skills as key barriers to effective classroom communication. These challenges limit their ability to actively contribute to discussions, connect meaningfully with peers, and fully engage in collaborative learning experiences. As one of the Participant briefly articulated this perspective:

“The challenges I have experience in attempting to engage in effective communication in the classroom is the lack of confidence and lack of listening to others.” (IDI-07)

(The challenges I have experience in attempting to engage in effective communication in the classroom is the lack of confidence and lack of listening to others.)

Moreover, participants face significant challenges with self-doubt and a lack of confidence, particularly in areas such as pronunciation, grammar, and expressing ideas cohesively. These difficulties can impede effective interpersonal communication as they work to overcome linguistic barriers and develop more polished and confident communication skills. As one of the Participant elucidated this struggle:

“I still have the doubt of myself. I’m not really confident when it comes speaking because I have problem in pronunciation and grammar, grammar making and still practicing on that. Still have that little problem when it comes to constructing my ideas so that is challenges that I face when I am trying to engage in effective interpersonal communication.” (FGD-04)

(I still have the doubt of myself. I am not really confident when it comes speaking because I have problem in pronunciation and grammar, grammar making and still practicing on that. Still have that little problem when it comes to constructing my ideas so that is challenges that I face when I am trying to engage in effective interpersonal communication.)

Additionally, many students highlight a fear of public speaking as a significant challenge, often hindering effective communication and active participation in class activities. This anxiety, rooted in the fear of making mistakes in front of peers, creates barriers to engagement and undermines their confidence in expressing ideas openly. As one of the Participant elaborates on this challenge:

“One of the common challenges that I face right now is fear of public speaking, fear of making mistakes in front of many people especially to your classmates kay kini man gud siya nga problem is nagahinder sya sa mga effective communication, maulaw pud ka magparticipate sa tanang activity and so on.” (FGD-03)

(One of the common challenges I face right now is the fear of public speaking, the fear of making mistakes in front of many people, especially to my classmates. This problem hinders effective communication, and it also makes me embarrassed to participate in all activities and so on.)

Having Disparities in Communicating with Varying Individuals. Elementary education students grapple with the complexities of communicating effectively with individuals across diverse contexts. While they demonstrate proficiency in expressing themselves and communicating with peers, challenges arise when engaging with professionals, necessitating the adoption of formal communication methods. This highlights the disparities in communication styles required when interacting with different individuals, underscoring the importance of adaptability and versatility in navigating diverse social and professional settings.

Being Able to Express and Communicating Effectively to Peers. Within the experiences shared by elementary education students, a notable aspect is their proficiency in communicating with peers. Participants highlight their ability to express themselves clearly and engage in meaningful communication with their peers, showcasing their confidence and competence in interpersonal interactions. This proficiency underscores the importance of peer-to-peer communication skills in fostering collaborative learning environments and building strong relationships within educational settings.

Elementary education students emphasized that their confidence in communicating effectively with peers is deeply tied to feeling understood and delivering their messages with clarity. This sense of mutual understanding is pivotal in boosting their perceived communication competence, fostering greater self-assurance in social interactions, and promoting meaningful connections. As one of the Participants stated:

“So, I feel good about my ability to communicate with my peers because masabtan nila akong gusto ipasabot.” (FGD-04)

(So, I feel good about my ability to communicate with my peers because they understand what I'm trying to convey.)

Furthermore, participants often experience a heightened sense of comfort and confidence in their communication abilities when a foundation of positive rapport and mutual understanding exists among classmates. These supportive dynamic fosters a sense of belonging, where individuals feel valued and respected, encouraging them to share their thoughts and ideas openly. In such an environment, participants are not only more likely to express themselves with clarity but also to ensure their messages are effectively conveyed and comprehended. According to one of the Participant:

“Well, sa sa akong mga classmates naman kay good kaayu labi na og ka vibes ra nimo the maka express ka tarung sa ilaha og masabtan jud nila and imong gusto ipasabot.” (FGD-02)

(With my classmates, it is really good, especially if you vibe well with them, you can express yourself properly to them, and they really understand what you're trying to convey.)

Likewise, they express confidence in their ability to communicate with peers, which allows them to effectively convey their ideas and build relationships. This confidence in communication plays a vital role in fostering connections and collaborations among peers, contributing to a positive and supportive communication environment. Based on the statement of one of the Participant:

“For me naman, when it comes to communicating with peers, kay confident ko which is ma express nako akong mga ideas sa ilaha og maka build kog relationship.” (FGD-03)

(For me, when it comes to communicating with peers, I am confident, which allows me to express my ideas to them and build relationships.)

Employing Formal Communication Methods When Communicating with Professionals. Among elementary education students, a distinct emphasis is placed on the importance of employing formal communication methods when interacting with professionals. Participants recognize the need to adapt their communication styles to suit the expectations of professional contexts, such as using formal language and adhering to professional etiquette. This emphasis reflects students' awareness of the significance of professionalism in professional settings and their commitment to presenting themselves in a manner that commands respect and credibility.

Participants note the presence of barriers when communicating with teachers, as the formal nature of such interactions requires a level of professionalism that differs from peer-to-peer communication. This contrast in communication styles between interacting with peers and engaging with educators can pose challenges in effectively expressing thoughts and ideas. As one of the Participant illustrates this point:

“...sa mga teachers is medyo naa syay barriers kay dapat mangud pud kung makipag storya sa mga professional dapat naay formality so mao to and difference sa akoang pag communicate between peers and teachers.” (FGD-04)

(With the teachers, there are some barriers because when talking to professionals, there should be a certain level of formality. So, that is the difference in how I communicate with peers and teachers.)

Moreover, participants express feelings of inadequacy when communicating with their teachers, which they attribute to the perceived necessity for using formal language due to their teachers' professional status. This perception can create a significant barrier to open communication, making students hesitant to express themselves freely. The fear of not meeting the expected level of formality may lead to anxiety and self-doubt, inhibiting their ability to engage in meaningful discussions. Based on one of the Participant:

“For me, I feel my ability to communicate with my teachers is not that good kay teacher man gud na sila so kailangan jud nimo og formal nga mga words to communicate them well because they are professionals.” (FGD-02)

(For me, I feel that my ability to communicate with my teachers is not that good because they are teachers, and you really need to use formal language to communicate with them well since they are professionals.)

Further, participants noted barriers in communication with teachers arising from the formality expected when interacting with professionals. This expectation for formality can create a perceived barrier that significantly influences how students communicate and express themselves. Students may feel pressured to adhere to specific linguistic norms, leading to anxiety and a lack of confidence in their ability to articulate their thoughts clearly. As one of the Participant highlights this challenge:

“However, when it comes to our teachers, there is quite barrier because of the formality that we can see as we need to use the formal context of communicating towards professionals.” (FGD-05)

(However, when it comes to our teachers, there is quite barrier because of the formality that we can see as we need to use the formal context of communicating towards professionals.)

Insights from BEED Students to Share with Their Peers

Table 9 displays the scrutinized and synthesized notions in the insights of BEED students with regards to interpersonal communication skills. As a result of the thematic analysis, 4 essential themes emerged namely: creating a positive and inclusive communication environment, seeking personal growth and self-development through interpersonal communication, cultivating interpersonal communication competencies, and applying holistic understanding through non-verbal cues.

Table 4. *Insights Of BEED Students That They Can Share to Their Fellow Students*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Significance of a supportive and healthy communication environment among peers.	Fostering a healthy environment where communication is healthy. Encouraging openness and support. Creating a supportive environment in communicating. Importance of creating a safe and supportive environment.	Promoting open communication and open mindedness Nurturing a supportive and inclusive learning environment	Creating a Positive and Inclusive Communication Environment	Communication Climate Theory
Impact of interpersonal communication skills on personal growth, adaptability, active listening, and relationship building.	Importance of actively listening and being open to suggestions and ideas. Being adaptive to feedback and open criticism. Being molded to become a better listener. Active listening develops personal growth. Willingness to open criticism.	Openness to suggestions and ideas Feedback and Continuous Self-Improvement	Seeking Personal Growth and Self-Development through Interpersonal Communication	Johari Window Model
Importance of active listening and encouragement for enhanced understanding, respect, growth, and effective communication	Encouragement is important in interpersonal communication improvements. Active listening promote understanding and respect. Active listening improves communication skills. Creating a supportive environment. Importance of active listening for creating a supportive environment. Active listening is a crucial skill for effective communication. Active listening fosters understanding and empathy.	Encouraging other people to communicate effectively Active Listening as a Catalyst for Deeper Understanding and Stronger Relationships	Cultivating Interpersonal Communication Competencies	Communication Competence Model

<p>Significance of nonverbal cues in interpersonal communication and their impact on understanding others' actions, emotions, and attitudes.</p>	<p>Significance of nonverbal cues in communication. Being aware of nonverbal cues helps in understanding others' actions and emotions as crucial in creating a supportive environment. Importance of nonverbal cues in communication in providing additional layers of meaning. Demonstrating the impact of nonverbal cues Non-verbal cues plays a vital role in successful interpersonal communication.</p>	<p>Role of Non-Verbal Cues in understanding other people's mental and emotional state</p> <p>Decoding nonverbal signals for underlying implications</p>	<p>Applying Holistic Understanding Through Non-Verbal Cues</p>	<p>Mehrabian's Nonverbal Communication Theory</p>
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Creating a Positive and Inclusive Communication Environment. Elementary education students underscored the importance of fostering such an environment through their lived experiences and coping mechanisms. Through interviews and focus group discussions, they highlighted the significance of promoting open communication and open-mindedness. Moreover, they emphasized the role of nurturing a supportive and inclusive learning environment, where everyone feels valued and accepted regardless of cultural background or differences.

Promoting Open Communication and Open Mindedness. During the interviews, participants highlighted the importance of promoting open communication and open-mindedness in their interactions. They discussed how fostering an environment where everyone feels comfortable expressing their thoughts and ideas encourages mutual respect and understanding. Participants emphasized their commitment to being receptive to diverse perspectives, which enhances their ability to engage in meaningful and constructive dialogues.

Elementary education students frequently recognize that open communication and mutual understanding are fundamental for effectively managing conflicts and building positive relationships within the classroom. These elements are crucial for creating a supportive and harmonious learning environment, where students feel heard and valued. Open communication allows for the expression of diverse perspectives and concerns, while mutual understanding helps in resolving misunderstandings and fostering empathy among peers. As one participant aptly noted:

“...dili jud malikayan nga nay Masilo nga mahitabo nay mga disagreement or dili magkasinabtanay then nay malain sa atua so ang conflict management nga akong ginabuhay kay gina communicate nako sila dapat open ta for communication sa uban through that masabtan natu ang atuang mga classmates o ubang tao. Makabalo ta nganong nalain sila saatua. Dili gyud dapat na iclose natu atung mind or ears aron ma aware ko ug unsa may dapat pa Nakong ichange.” (IDI-03)

(It is unavoidable that there will be misunderstandings or disagreements, which can lead to some negative feelings between us. Therefore, the conflict management approach I use involves communicating with them and ensuring that we are open to communication with others. Through this, we can better understand our classmates or other individuals. We will know why they feel upset with us. We should not close our minds or ears to be aware of what we need to change.)

Moreover, they also share a valuable insight on how personal experiences of growth through feedback can transform workplace culture. By highlighting instances where they benefited from constructive criticism, they can illustrate the positive impact of feedback on professional development and team dynamics. This can foster a culture of open dialogue, where feedback is embraced as a tool for continuous improvement rather than seen as a threat. As one of the Participant said:

“I inspire them by sharing personal experiences where I've grown from feedback and demonstrate a willingness to learn and improve. Encouraging open dialogue and create a supportive learning where feedback is viewed as a constructive tool for growth rather than criticism.” (FGD-06)

(I inspire them by sharing personal experiences where I've grown from feedback and demonstrate a willingness to learn and improve. Encouraging open dialogue and create a supportive learning where feedback is viewed as a constructive tool for growth rather than criticism.)

Nurturing a Supportive and Inclusive Learning Environment. Participants underscored the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment during interviews and focus group discussions. They emphasized their efforts to ensure that all individuals feel valued, respected, and included, regardless of their cultural backgrounds or differences. They highlighted practices such as active listening, empathy, and open communication as essential tools in nurturing this environment.

Participants of this study highlighted how fostering a non-judgmental and supportive environment encourages continuous improvement in interpersonal communication. By promoting open dialogue and mutual respect, individuals feel more comfortable discussing their communication challenges and seeking constructive feedback. As one of the Participant emphasized:

“So for me to inspire peers to seek opportunities for continuous improvement in terms of interpersonal communication skills is kaning I will create a supportive environment in which it will foster a supportive in and in a judgmental atmosphere where peers feel comfortable in discussing communication challenges and seeking feedback and at the same time create a supportive environment.” (FGD-01)

(For me, to inspire peers to seek opportunities for continuous improvement in terms of interpersonal communication skills, I will create a supportive environment. It will foster a supportive, non-judgmental atmosphere where peers feel comfortable discussing communication challenges and seeking feedback. At the same time, I will create a supportive environment.)

In addition, elementary education students underscored the vital role of creating a safe and supportive environment in developing interpersonal communication skills. They emphasized that when trust and a non-judgmental atmosphere are cultivated, individuals feel more at ease sharing their thoughts, discussing challenges, and seeking constructive feedback. This openness not only strengthens communication but also encourages self-awareness and resilience. As one of the Participant highlighted:

“So, for me, I would create a supportive environment in which I would foster a safe and supportive environment where my peers feel comfortable and comfortable sharing their communication challenges and seeking feedback. Encouraging and an atmosphere of trust and non-judgment can motivate others to be open to receiving feedback and actively working on their communication skills.” (FGD-04)

Seeking Personal Growth and Self-Development through Interpersonal Communication. Participants shared insights into their journey of self-discovery and improvement through their interpersonal interactions. They emphasized the importance of being open to suggestions and ideas as a catalyst for personal growth. Additionally, they highlighted the value of feedback and continuous self-improvement in their communication practices. Embracing constructive criticism and utilizing it as a tool for reflection and refinement, participants demonstrate a commitment to honing their interpersonal skills and fostering meaningful connections with others.

Openness To Suggestions and Ideas. During the interviews, participants emphasized the importance of maintaining openness to suggestions and ideas in their interpersonal interactions. They discussed their willingness to actively listen and consider diverse viewpoints, recognizing that this openness fosters a collaborative and innovative atmosphere. Participants highlighted how being receptive to feedback and new perspectives helps them grow both personally and professionally.

In this study, participants provided valuable insights into the importance of open communication and respect in collaborative group activities and projects. They emphasized that encouraging the sharing of diverse ideas and suggestions is crucial for teams to effectively address challenges and develop innovative solutions. This collaborative approach fosters an environment where every member feels valued and empowered to contribute, ultimately enhancing the quality of the group’s output. As one of the Participant stated:

“...it depends on a situation na if naa mi activities gud kanang magbuhat mig project ahmm.. dili jud natu malikayan na atung peers is mag share pud sailang idea ba or suggestions sa kana na activities. kita tanan is lahi-lahi manjud ta ug ideas so ahh. Dili lang natu buhaton na mahimong babag to solve sa isa ka problema so I adapt lang natu ilang suggestions and katu pud na mga suggestions is istoyahan pud natu sila if kani bai lang gipang suggest is makatabang jud b ani. E communicate natu sila ug atrung , e respect sila so that, masolusyonan na ang problema.” (IDI-01)

(It depends on the situation, like if we have activities where we are doing a project, it is inevitable for our peers to share their ideas or suggestions for those activities. We all have different ideas, so we should not just dismiss them because it might be the solution to a problem. We adapt to their suggestions, and sometimes, those suggestions can really help. We communicate with them properly, we respect them, so that we can solve the problem together.)

Additionally, they pointed out the significance of being receptive to feedback and learning from others' perspectives to enhance personal growth and communication skills. This highlights how actively seeking and integrating feedback can improve not only individual communication skills but also foster better interpersonal relationships. Embracing diverse viewpoints and constructive criticism contributes to both personal and collective growth. As one of the Participant indicated:

“For me maam, I can convey my experiences to my fellow students by being open to feedback from my peers and be willing to learn from their perspectives to learn as well.” (IDI-02)

(For me, I can share my experiences with my fellow students by being open to feedback from them and being willing to learn from their perspectives.)

Further, they also offered an insight into improving interpersonal communication skills can facilitate openness to suggestions and self-improvement. They noted that individuals can create an environment conducive to growth and collaboration. This statement illustrates how developing strong communication skills enables individuals to be more receptive to feedback and better engage in meaningful exchanges with others. During the interview, one of the Participant expressed that:

“So, through my interpersonal communication skills, nakatabang gyud sya nga mas open ko for suggestions sa uban o unsay pay need ichange pa saakong self. then naging open for communication ko sa ilaha.” (IDI-03)

(So, through my interpersonal communication skills, it really helps me to be more open to suggestions from others or what else needs to be changed about myself. Then, I became open for communication with them.)

Feedback And Continuous Self-Improvement. During the interviews, participants highlighted the critical role of feedback in their journey toward continuous self-improvement. They discussed their proactive approach to seeking and embracing constructive criticism, viewing it as an essential tool for personal and professional growth. Participants emphasized the importance of reflecting on feedback to identify areas for development and implement necessary changes.

Elementary education students highlighted the importance of developing interpersonal communication skills as a pathway to personal growth and humility. They emphasized that practicing active listening and being receptive to constructive feedback can help individuals overcome selfish tendencies, fostering a mindset of continuous self-improvement and greater empathy toward others. Based on one of the Participant:

“So when it comes to interpersonal communication skills, it mold me about the way na dili naku nagging selfish when it comes to listening to, because active listening develop your personality to change you as a person because dili manta perpekto, willing ko mo adapt , willing ko maminaw sa uban sa uban and ipractice tung mga skills and corrections na akong na adapt sailaha . (IDI-01)

(So, when it comes to interpersonal communication skills, it molds me to not be selfish when it comes to listening to others. Active listening develops your personality and changes you as a person because nobody is perfect. I am willing to adapt, willing to listen to others, and practice the skills and corrections that I have learned from them.)

Furthermore, participants also articulated the importance of active listening and willingness to adapt to others' opinions and suggestions for personal development. This emphasizes that being receptive to others' feedback and adapting accordingly not only fosters better interpersonal relationships but also ultimately benefits one's own growth and development. According to one of the Participant:

“Kabalo napud ko maminaw ug musabot sa ilahang mga opinion ug willing napud ko I adapt kung unsa man ilang mga suggestion sa mga tao maam or feedback nila kay at the end of the day ako raman japon maka benefit ana maam.” (IDI-02)

(I also know how to listen and understand their opinions, and I am willing to adapt to whatever suggestions or feedback they have, because at the end of the day, I will still benefit from it.)

Cultivating Interpersonal Communication Competencies. Elementary education students highlighted their efforts to enhance their communication skills through their lived experiences and coping mechanisms. They stressed the importance of encouraging others to communicate effectively as a means of fostering stronger connections. Moreover, they highlighted the role of active listening as a catalyst for deeper understanding and stronger relationships. Through attentive listening and empathetic engagement, they not only enhance their own communication abilities but also foster mutual respect and trust within their interpersonal interactions.

Encouraging Other People to Communicate Effectively. Participants stressed the importance of encouraging others to communicate effectively, during the interview. They discussed their efforts to model good communication practices, such as active listening, clear expression, and respectful dialogue. Participants emphasized creating an environment where everyone feels comfortable and confident to share their thoughts and ideas. This supportive approach not only enhances interpersonal relationships but also builds a community where effective communication is valued, leading to more productive and harmonious interactions.

In this study, elementary education students emphasized the essential role of fostering a culture of encouragement and respect in communication. They conveyed that when communication is approached with a focus on uplifting individuals and valuing their contributions, it transforms into a powerful tool for improvement rather than merely a means of sharing information. This perspective highlights the importance of creating an environment where every participant feels valued, heard, and motivated to express their thoughts. As one of the Participant stated:

“...it is important to encourage people when it comes to communication, encourage every individual that when communicating is important to respect their ideas, to listen, listen others feedback because communication is not just sharing of information, but it is about imparting ideas to improve what must to be improved when it comes to interpersonal communication.” (IDI-01)

(It is important to encourage people when it comes to communication, encourage every individual that when communicating is important to respect their ideas, to listen, listen others feedback because communication is not just sharing of information, but it is about imparting ideas to improve what must to be improved when it comes to interpersonal communication.)

In addition, participants emphasized the critical role of encouraging their peers to engage as active listeners. This approach reflects their recognition of the importance of mutual understanding in enhancing communication effectiveness. By fostering an environment where active listening is prioritized, students can significantly improve not only their own communication skills but also the overall dynamics of their interactions. According to one of the Participant:

“akong buhaton kay e encourage nko akong peers maam na maging active listener ming duha arun magkasinabot mi maam. In that way, nag show mi ug respect both ideas and nagging open for communication and changes.” (IDI-02)

(What I do, ma'am, is I encourage my peers to become active listeners so that we can understand each other. In that way, we show

respect for both ideas and become open to communication and changes.)

Moreover, they emphasized the importance of encouraging peers to practice active listening and maintain openness in communication. By promoting these habits, they strive to foster mutual understanding, show respect for diverse viewpoints, and gain valuable insights into different perspectives. This approach not only strengthens interpersonal relationships but also enhances overall communication effectiveness. As stated by one of the Participant:

“Para saakoa maam eencourage nko akong mga peers na ipadayun ang pagiging active listener and open to communication maam kay in that way man gud maam mas masabtan nimo sila ug nag show kag respect sa ubang tao ug makit an pud nimo ang point of view tapos makabuo kag good communication.” (IDI-02)

(For me, ma'am, I encourage my peers to continue being active listeners and open to communication because in that way, you can understand them better and show respect to others, and you can also see their point of view and build good communication.)

Also, they highlighted the significance of actively promoting and practicing active listening among peers and coworkers. Encouraging this skill not only enhances communication but also supports personal growth and development. By fostering active listening, individuals contribute to a more collaborative and understanding environment, strengthening both individual and group communication dynamics. Based on one of the Participant:

“I will encourage all students or to my co-students that I will encourage to my co-workers to ahmm engaged active listening because it can help as to mold us as a person and also to to us for ahmm ka ng maka-gain ta sa active listninging og ka ng, ka ng good communication.” (IDI-05)

(I will encourage all students or my co-students, as well as my co-workers, to engage in active listening because it can help us mold ourselves as individuals and also help us gain good communication skills.)

Furthermore, suggests the significance of creating a supportive environment through sharing personal experiences and fostering encouragement. This highlights that sharing personal experiences not only promotes a culture of support and growth but also helps peers feel more secure and motivated to engage in risk-taking and learning opportunities. In accordance with the statement of one the Participant:

“By sharing personal experience, a supporting and encourage growth I would create a supportive environment where my peers feel encourage and safe to take risk and learn from this mistake.” (IDI-06)

(By sharing personal experience, a supporting and encourage growth I would create a supportive environment where my peers feel encourage and safe to take risk and learn from this mistake.)

Active Listening as A Catalyst for Deeper Understanding and Stronger Relationships. During the interviews, participants highlighted active listening as a fundamental component in fostering deeper understanding and stronger relationships. They discussed how attentively listening to others, without interrupting or prematurely judging, allows them to fully grasp the perspectives and emotions of their peers. This empathetic approach helps build trust and respect, making others feel heard and valued. Participants emphasized that active listening not only enhances communication but also strengthens interpersonal connections, as it demonstrates genuine interest and concern for others' experiences.

Elementary education students reflected during the interview the significance of active listening in fostering deeper understanding and building stronger relationships. They emphasize the importance of encouraging peers to practice active listening through demonstration, emphasizing techniques like asking open-ended questions and paraphrasing to ensure comprehension. As stated by one of the Participant:

“One lesson I have learned about the importance of active listening is that it fosters deeper understanding and stronger relationships. And I encourage, I encourage peers to practice it by demonstrating attentive listening during conversations as well as to emphasize the value of asking ended questions, paraphrasing to confirm understanding and providing support feedback. And the most important, create a supportive environment where everyone feels heard and valued. Also encouraged to active listening among to the peers.” (FGD-06)

Additionally, participants emphasized the importance of active listening as a vital skill for fostering effective communication and deeper understanding. This emphasis illustrates that active listening is not merely a passive reception of words but a dynamic and engaging process that enhances the clarity of communication while allowing individuals to grasp the emotional and contextual nuances embedded in a message. According to one of the Participant:

“Active listening is very important skill that we faster effective communication and deeper understanding and active listening allow us to fully comprehend the message that being conveyed. By giving our full attention to the speaker, we can know the emotions and underlying meanings in their words and demonstrating active listening skills.” (FGD-03)

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underlying meanings in their words and demonstrating active listening skills.)

Also, Participants also highlighted the importance of active listening, emphasizing its critical role in cultivating understanding and empathy. This skill transcends the mere act of hearing words; it involves fully engaging with the speaker and striving to grasp their perspectives and experiences. Individuals create deeper connections with others, enhancing their ability to empathize and respond compassionately during interactions. As one of the Participant expressed:

“I have learned one thing about the importance of active listening and the answer is understanding and empathy, in which active listening allow allows me to truly understand others perspective and experiences, which also fosters empathy and compassion in our interactions.” (FGD-01)

(I have learned one thing about the importance of active listening and the answer is understanding and empathy, in which active listening allow allows me to truly understand others perspective and experiences, which also fosters empathy and compassion in our interactions.)

Applying Holistic Understanding Through Non-Verbal Cues. Participants discussed the critical role of non-verbal communication in their interactions, highlighting its importance in achieving a holistic understanding of others. Through interviews and focus group discussions, they emphasized how non-verbal cues help them grasp the mental and emotional states of their peers, facilitating more empathetic and responsive communication. This nuanced approach to communication allows them to respond more effectively and sensitively, fostering deeper connections and promoting a more supportive and understanding environment.

Role Of Non-Verbal Cues in Understanding Other People’s Mental And Emotional State. Participants underscored the significance of non-verbal cues in deciphering the mental and emotional states of others during the interviews. They emphasized the importance of being attuned to non-verbal signals, as they provide context and depth to interpersonal interactions. This heightened awareness enables participants to build stronger connections and cultivate deeper understanding in their relationships, ultimately contributing to more meaningful and empathetic communication experiences.

Participants in this study underscored the importance of non-verbal cues, including hand gestures and facial expressions, in communication. They provide an example of how observing a classmate's sadness prompts them to approach with empathy and respect, recognizing the potential need for support while also respecting boundaries if the classmate is not ready to share. According to one of the Participant:

“Para saako is explain nako sailaha maam na importante kaayu ang non-verbal cues since included dra ang hand gestures, facing expression.” (IDI-2)

(For me, I would explain to them the importance of non-verbal cues, which includes hand gestures and facial expressions.)

In addition, participants shared the significance of understanding non-verbal cues in enhancing interpersonal communication skills, especially regarding their future roles as educators. They emphasized that non-verbal communication—such as gestures, facial expressions, posture, and eye contact—plays a crucial role in conveying emotions and intentions. As one of the Participants mentioned:

“So for me, ipasabot lang gyud natu sailaha nga importantge gyud nga makasabot ta sa mga non-verbal cues. Through that mas ma improved natu ang atung interpersonal communication skills as na mention pud nako gaina as a future teacher dapat kabalo sad ta sa mga actions sa mga taong naka palibot satua.” (IDI-03)

(So for me, we should really understand the importance of understanding non-verbal cues. Through that, we can improve our interpersonal communication skills. As I mentioned earlier, as a future teacher, it's also important for us to understand the actions of the people around us.)

Decoding Nonverbal Signals for Underlying Implications. Throughout the interviews, participants emphasized the importance of deciphering nonverbal signals to uncover underlying implications in interpersonal communication. They highlighted the significance of being attentive to nonverbal cues, as they provide valuable context and contribute to more accurate and empathetic communication. Participants shared examples of how decoding nonverbal signals has helped them navigate complex social situations, resolve conflicts, and strengthen relationships. This ability to read between the lines fosters greater empathy, trust, and connection in their interactions, ultimately enhancing the quality of their communication experiences.

Elementary education students elaborated on the importance of non-verbal cues, such as facial expressions, gestures, body language, and tone of voice, in effective communication. They articulated that these non-verbal signals add essential depth and richness to interpersonal interactions, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of messages conveyed during conversations. According to one of the Participant:

“...because non-verbal cues such as facial expressions the gestures, body language of the tone of voice, it provides additional layers of meaning to our communication, so that they can convey emotions, attitudes and also intentions that we’re alone me not fully express, so by this by paying attention to non-verbal cues we can better understand the through message being convey in avoid misinterpretation.” (IDI-05)

(Because non-verbal cues such as facial expressions the gestures, body language of the tone of voice, it provides additional layers of meaning to our communication, so that they can convey emotions, attitudes and also intentions that we're alone me not fully express, so by this by paying attention to non-verbal cues we can better understand the through message being convey in avoid misinterpretation.)

Moreover, they suggested a practical approach to conveying the importance of non-verbal cues by demonstrating their relevance through real-life situations and facial expressions. By showcasing how non-verbal cues influence interactions, individuals can better understand their significance and impact which will not only raises awareness but also promotes a deeper understanding of the role non-verbal communication plays in effective communication and relationship-building. Based on one of the Participant:

"I can communicate my fellow students the importance of non-verbal cues by showing their situation and facial expression in this way they will know the importance and impact of non-verbal cues in interactions." (IDI-07)

(I can communicate my fellow students the importance of non-verbal cues by showing their situation and facial expression in this way they will know the importance and impact of non-verbal cues in interactions.)

Furthermore, participants underscored the vital role of nonverbal cues, such as body language and tone of voice, in achieving successful interpersonal communication. They articulated that these nonverbal signals are not merely supplementary elements of communication; rather, they serve as fundamental components that significantly shape the meaning of verbal exchanges. As one of the Participant stated:

"We all know that nonverbal cues like body language and tone of voice are vital in successful interpersonal communication as they convey emotions and attitudes and at in intentions and also awareness of these cues enhances understanding and fosters better connections with others." (FGD-06)

(We all know that nonverbal cues like body language and tone of voice are vital in successful interpersonal communication as they convey emotions and attitudes and at in intentions and also awareness of these cues enhances understanding and fosters better connections with others.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The present study on the interpersonal communication skills of first year elementary education students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology, utilizes a mixed methods approach, employing the convergent parallel approach. Table 10 outlines the salient quantitative and qualitative findings, presenting focal points in the first column, which contains the aspects or focal points of the study. This is followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third columns, respectively. The findings from the quantitative phase typically consist of the items in indicator, while the qualitative findings, which display the identified responses, confirm or disconfirm the quantitative results. The fourth column indicates the nature of the data integration, and the fifth column contains the axiological implications based on the data described in the preceding columns.

Table 5. Joint Display Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

<i>Aspect or Focal Points</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implications</i>
Students' intrapersonal communication skills in terms of environment control	Table 2 on the level of intrapersonal communication skills in terms of environment control Item No. 1 about finding easily the right words to express myself with a mean of 3.68	Table 9 on the experiences and coping mechanism of first year BEED students with regards to their interpersonal skills has codes of employing formal communication methods when communicating with professionals highlighting the essential theme having disparities in communicating with varying individuals.	Merging-Converging	Students who develop the ability to find the right words for self-expression and adapt their communication styles to different audiences within a nurturing educational environment will be better equipped with self-efficacy and empowered to navigate diverse social and professional settings effectively.
	Table 2 on the level of intrapersonal communication skills in terms of environment control item no. 4 about excelling in expressing myself verbally with a mean of 3.18	Table 9 on the experiences and coping mechanism of first year BEED students with regards to their interpersonal skills has codes of having flexible communication methods highlighting the essential theme employing cross-cultural communication competence.	Merging-Converging	Students excelling in verbal self-expression and cross-cultural communication competence will be well-prepared for diverse settings.
Students' intrapersonal communication	Table 2 on the level of intrapersonal communication skills	Table 9 on the experiences and coping mechanism of first year BEED students with regards to	Merging-Converging	Students empowered to disclose feelings appropriately across contexts communicates

skills in terms of self-disclosure	in terms of self-disclosure item no. 2 about revealing how I feel to others with a mean of 3.03	their interpersonal skills has codes of being able to express and communicate effectively to peers highlighting the essential theme having disparities in communicating with varying individuals.		authentically yet adaptively.
Students' intercultural sensitivity in terms of assertiveness	Table 2 on the level of intrapersonal communication skills in terms of assertiveness item no. 3 about having trouble in standing up myself with a mean of 3.45	Table 9 on the experiences and coping mechanism of first year BEED students with regards to their interpersonal skills has codes of lack of confidence when speaking in public highlighting the essential theme encountering challenges in conveying messages in public speaking. Table 9 on the experiences and coping mechanism of first year BEED students with regards to their interpersonal skills has codes of failing to effectively convey ideas highlighting the essential theme encountering challenges in conveying messages in public speaking. Table 9 on the experiences and coping mechanism of first year BEED students with regards to their interpersonal skills has codes of being anxious when talking in front of many people highlighting the essential theme encountering challenges in conveying messages in public speaking.	Merging-Converging	Students bolstered in assertiveness and public speaking skills within an empowering educational environment gains efficacy in cross-cultural communication.

Students' intrapersonal communication skills in terms of environment control. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on environment control rated as high is Item No.1 about finding easily the right words to express myself with a mean of 3.68. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is themed as having disparities in communicating with varying individuals. From an axiological perspective, students who develop the ability to find the right words for self-expression and adapt their communication styles to different audiences within a nurturing educational environment will be better equipped with self-efficacy and empowered to navigate diverse social and professional settings effectively. Moreover, the item number 4 on environment control excelling in expressing myself verbally with a mean

Students' intrapersonal communication skills in terms of self-disclosure. In quantitative phase, No. 2 on self-disclosure revealing how I feel to others with a mean of 3.03 and a description of high. This result is connected to the qualitative finding, which themes having disparities in communicating with varying individuals. From an axiological perspective, students empowered to disclose feelings appropriately across contexts communicates authentically yet adaptively. At this point, it is acknowledged that quantitative and qualitative data converges.

Students' intercultural sensitivity in terms of assertiveness. In quantitative phase, the specific item on assertiveness rated high is Item No. 3 having trouble in standing up myself with a mean of 3.45. It is connected with the qualitative findings, which themes encountering challenges in conveying messages in public speaking. From an axiological perspective, students bolstered in assertiveness and public speaking skills within an empowering educational environment gains efficacy in cross-cultural communication. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitative data in this aspect.

Intervention Scheme

Interpersonal communication, defined as the exchange of ideas, information, feelings, and intentions through messages and signals, is fundamental to both personal and professional relationships, playing a crucial role in daily interactions. Effective communication encompasses various elements, including face-to-face interactions, where individuals utilize voice, facial expressions, body language, and gestures to convey their thoughts (Future Learn, 2022). Despite its importance, there is a notable gap in research focusing on the interpersonal communication skills of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) teacher education students, particularly concerning aspects such as environmental control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management, and immediacy (Sword, 2020; Ding,

2021).

Table 6. *Intervention Scheme Based on the Findings of the Study*

<i>Problems</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Person In-Charge</i>	<i>Time Element</i>
Deficiencies in active listening and nonverbal communication skills	To enhance students' active listening abilities and understanding of nonverbal cues.	Active Listening and Nonverbal Communication Skills Workshop: A targeted workshop focused on training students to interpret and utilize nonverbal signals effectively. This workshop includes interactive activities and role-playing exercises to practice active listening and enhance respectful interactions.	Faculty Communication Department	Once per semester
Weak interpersonal communication skills affecting academic engagement and relationships	To strengthen students' interpersonal communication skills for better collaboration and relationship building.	Interpersonal Communication and Relationship Building Seminar: A seminar designed to provide students with practical strategies for effective communication, relationship building, and personal growth. This seminar includes group discussions, case studies, and activities that promote adaptability in various educational contexts.	Faculty Development Office	Once per semester

The findings of this study underscore the critical need for BEED teacher education students to enhance their interpersonal communication skills to succeed in diverse educational settings. As a recommended intervention scheme, Active Listening and Nonverbal Communication Skills Workshop is designed to address deficiencies in active listening and the use of nonverbal cues, which are pivotal for effective communication. This workshop offers targeted training to improve students' abilities to interpret and utilize nonverbal signals, thereby fostering a deeper understanding and more respectful interactions.

Additionally, Interpersonal Communication and Relationship Building Seminar is an essential intervention to strengthen students' interpersonal communication skills, crucial for academic engagement, collaboration, and the development of strong student-teacher relationships. This seminar provides students with practical strategies for effective communication, relationship building, and personal growth, enhancing their adaptability and effectiveness in various educational contexts. Together, these interventions equip BEED teacher education students with the comprehensive communication skills necessary to thrive as educators, fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment for their future students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the level of intrapersonal communication skills among BEED teacher education students is high in terms of environment control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management, and immediacy. Hence, this indicates that the following indicators are oftentimes manifested by the selected BEED students.

Second, the thematic analysis of the qualitative data was done based on the responses gained through the conduct of in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD). The results gave more information about the lived experiences of BEED students in terms of their interpersonal communication skills. Qualitatively, the education students shared their experiences and coping mechanisms with regards to interacting with other people. The following themes emerged: Employing Cross-Cultural Communication Competence, Embracing Criticism or Personal Growth and Professional Development, Encountering Challenges in Conveying Messages in Public Speaking, and Having Disparities in Communicating with Varying Individuals.

Third, based on the participants' responses on the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, other themes were identified which show the insights shared by elementary education students with regards to their interpersonal communication skills. These are the following themes emerged: Creating a Positive and Inclusive Communication Environment, Seeking Personal Growth and Self-Development through Interpersonal Communication, Cultivating Interpersonal Communication Competencies, and Applying Holistic Understanding Through Non-Verbal Cues.

Fourth, to better understand the interpersonal communication skills of elementary education students, the responses were analyzed thematically to confirm the quantitative results of this study. Both findings from the two phases are integrated based on the nature plan. The status of interpersonal communication skills of elementary education students based on the quantitative results showed that it converged to the data gained from the qualitative phase. Both quantitative and qualitative results confirm that elementary education students display interpersonal communication skills upon interacting with other people.

Lastly, through the different response of the BEED students regarding their interpersonal communication skills in the lens of

experiences and in quantitative findings, the researcher come up with intervention schemes such as interpersonal communication and relationship building seminar and the active listening and nonverbal communication skills workshop. Wherein, this will help students enhance their interpersonal communication skills that would help them for their personal and professional growth.

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations have been formulated to enhance the interpersonal communication skills of BEED teacher education students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST). Firstly, it is recommended to integrate regular communication skills workshops into the curriculum. These workshops should focus on various forms of communication, including verbal, non-verbal, listening, and assertiveness. Practical activities such as role-playing, group discussions, and presentations can provide hands-on experience, further developing these essential skills.

To foster a supportive and engaging learning environment, enhancing the quality of student-teacher interactions is crucial. Teachers should receive training in effective communication strategies to establish trust and rapport with students. Regular feedback sessions and open communication channels can help students feel more comfortable seeking help, asking questions, and participating in class discussions. Additionally, establishing peer mentorship programs can help students develop their communication skills in a more informal and supportive setting. Senior students or alumni with strong communication abilities can mentor junior students, providing guidance and feedback on their interpersonal communication.

Also, leveraging technology can also enhance communication skills training. Online forums, virtual discussions, and digital storytelling tools can be integrated into the curriculum to provide diverse communication platforms. This approach also prepares students for the increasing reliance on digital communication in educational settings. Furthermore, providing opportunities for field-based learning experiences, such as internships, community service projects, and field trips, can expose students to real-world communication scenarios. These experiences help students practice and refine their communication skills in various contexts, enhancing their confidence and adaptability.

Moreover, collaborating with journal publishers to disseminate the findings of this study can raise awareness about the importance of interpersonal communication skills in education. Publications can highlight best practices, innovative strategies, and successful case studies, contributing to the broader educational community's understanding and appreciation of these skills. Additionally, offering professional development programs for instructors on the latest communication techniques and educational psychology can equip them with the skills to better support their students. Workshops on active listening, conflict resolution, and culturally responsive teaching can be particularly beneficial.

Finally, implementing a system of continuous assessment and feedback for communication skills can help track student progress and identify areas for improvement. Regular self-assessments, peer evaluations, and instructor feedback can create a comprehensive understanding of each student's communication abilities.

References

- Abzeytov, A., & Isabekova, S. (2020). Assessment of Cross-cultural Communicative Competence. *Велес*, (6-1), 57-67.
- Agnihotri, A. (2022, December 23). 10 Impactful Ways To Boost Interpersonal Skills In Students. *The Hindustan Times*. <https://www.hindustantimes.com/Lifestyle/Relationships/10-Impactful-Ways-To-Boost-Interpersonal-Skills-In-Students-101671778138694.html>
- Allen, S. (2020). The Effect Of The Environmental Control On Interpersonal Communication Skills On Nursing Students. *Google Scholar*. <https://www.skillsyouneed.com/ips/interpersonal-communication.html>
- Allport, G. W. 1954. *The Nature Of Prejudice*. Cambridge, MA: Perseus Books.
- Altman, I., & Taylor, D., (1973). *Social Penetration: The Development Of Interpersonal Relationships*. Newyork: Holt, Rinehart And Winston
<https://www.uky.edu/~Drlane/Capstone/Interpersonal/Socpen.html#:text=The%20social%20penetration%20theory%20states,Date%3A%201973>
- Amin, A., Alimni, A., Kurniawan*, D.A., Triani, E., & Septi, S.E. (2023). INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS ON STUDENT DISCIPLINE: ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTS OF ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS LEARNING. *Lentera Pendidikan : Jurnal Ilmu Tarbiyah Dan Keguruan*.
- Amir, H. S., & Jakob, J. C. (2020). Male And Female Teachers' Turn Taking Strategies In EFL Classroom Interaction. *International Journal Of Progressive Sciences And Technologies (IJPSAT)*, 19(1), 176–182.
- Amitii, F. (2020). Synchronous And Asynchronous E-Learning. *European Journal Of Open Education And E-Learning Studies*, 5(2), 60-70. Available At: <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejoe.v5i2.3313>. Among Five Approaches. 2nd Edn. Sage Publications, London, UK
- Asido, M. (2019) The Interpersonal Communication Skills And Academic Performance Of Grade 8 Students Of Public High Schools In Tagaytay City. *Ascendens Asia Journal Of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts / Articles*.

<https://Ojs.Aaresearchindex.Com/Index.Php/AAJMRA/Article/View/10134>

Azlina, N., Amin, S. M., & Lukito, A. (2018). Creativity Of Field-Dependent And Field-Independent Students In Posing Mathematical Problems. In *Journal Of Physics: Conference Series*, 947(1). IOP Publishing.

Ban, A., & Bucur, M. (2023). "NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION – A STUDY ON ENGINEERING STUDENTS ". *Professional Communication And Translation Studies*.

Bandura, A. (1977). *Social Learning Theory*. Prentice-Hall.

Berger, C. R. & Calabrese, R. J. (1975). Some Explorations In Initial Interaction And Beyond: Toward A Developmental Theory Of Interpersonal Communication. *Human Communication Research*, 1, 99-112.

Berger, C. R. (1986). Uncertain Outcome Values In Predicted Relationships: Uncertainty Reduction Theory Then And Now. *Human Communication Research*, 13, 34-38.

Boginskaya, O.A. (2023). Tentativeness Vs Assertiveness: Metadiscourse Choices Of Russian Engineering Writers. *NSU Vestnik. Series: Linguistics And Intercultural Communication*.

Bozkurt, A., & Stracke, C. M. (2023). The Shift Toward Openness In Education And The Implications For Learning Ecosystems And Ecologies. In *Distributed Learning Ecosystems: Concepts, Resources, And Repositories* (Pp. 31-46). Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden.

Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. (1987). *Studies In Interactional Sociolinguistics: Politeness: Some Universals In Language Usage Series Number 4: Some Universals In Language Usage*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/Cbo9780511813085>

Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical Bases Of Com-Municative Approaches To Second Language Teaching And Testing. *Applied Linguistics*, 1(1), 1-47.

Chiaro, C. (2021, September 27). Why Communication Skills Are Essential In College. Teachhub. <https://www.teachhub.com/teaching-strategies/2021/09/why-communication-skills-are-essential-in-college/>

Chowdary Kandepu, T.D., N, L., Mathi, M.C., Midathada, S.K., Kishore Mallireddy, H.S., & Marapatla, H.S. (2023). Enhanced Communication Through Isolated Sign Language. *2023 International Conference On Self Sustainable Artificial Intelligence Systems (ICSSAS)*, 1046-1051.

Clevinger, K., Albert, E. & Raiche, E. (2019). Supervisor Self-Disclosure: Supervisees' Perceptions Of Positive Supervision Experiences. *American Psychological Association*, 13(3), 222-226. <https://doi.org/10.1037/Tep0000236>

Coker, W. (2022). Exploration Of Public-Speaking Anxiety Among Novice Instructors At A Ghanaian University. *The African Journal Of Information And Communication (AJIC)*.

Conklin, A. 2021. Immediacy Definition, Verbal And Nonverbal Immediacy, And Examples Of Verbal And Nonverbal Communication. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/immediacy-in-communication-definition-lesson-quiz.html>

Cresswell, K.S. & Clark K. (2007). *Mustering The Will And Skill For Change*.

Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, And Evaluating Quantitative And Qualitative Research* (4th Ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill.

Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry And Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches* (3rd Ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage

Creswell, J.W. (2007). *Qualitative Inquiry And Research Design: Choosing*

Creswell, J.W. (2009). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative And Mixed*

Cui, Z. (2022). The Impact Of EFL Teachers' Open-Mindedness And Immediacy On Their Social Intelligence: A T

David, T. (2019). How Self Concept Impacts Communication: An Overview. *Textbooklibrary*. <https://doi.org/10.29593.59295.295>

De Vries, G., Rietkerk, M., & Kooger, R. (2019). The Hassle Factor As A Psychologicalbarrier To A Green Home.*Journal Of Consumer Policy*. Advance Online Publication.<https://doi.org/10.1007/S10603-019-09410-7>.

Delos Reyes, R. D. G., & Torio, V. A. G. (2020). The Relationship Of Expert Teacher–Learner Rapport And Learner Autonomy In The CVIF-Dynamic Learning Program. *The Asiapacific Education Researcher*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S40299-020-00532-Y>

Dickinson, A. (2017). Communicating With The Online Student: The Impact Of E-Mail Tone On Student Performance And Teacher Evaluations. *J. Educ. Online* 14, 1–10. Doi: 10.9743/Jeo.2017.14.2.5

- Dixit, A. 2018. "Communication Is Incomplete Without Feedback" Volume 2, July 2018 ISSN 2581-5504
- Dovidio, J. F., Gaertner, S. L. And Kawakami, K. 2003. Intergroup Contact: The Past, Present, And The Future. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations*, 6(1), 5-21. Doi: 10.1177/1368430203006001009
- Erikson, E. H. (1994). *Identity: Youth And Crisis*. WW Norton & Company.
- Faelden, J. 2019. *Perceived Personality Traits Of Deaf Students Of Cagayan De Oro National High School: Basis For Intervention*.
- Feng, H. (2015). Politeness Theory. In *The International Encyclopedia Of Interpersonal Communication* (Pp. 1–13). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118540190.wbeic164>
- Fioravanti, M.L., De Oliveira Sestito, C.D., De Deus, W.S., Scatalon, L.P., & Barbosa, E.F. (2022). Role-Playing Games For Fostering Communication And Negotiation Skills. *IEEE Transactions On Education*, 65, 384-393.
- Franciska, H., Hadhazi, B. (2020) Students' Assertive Communication Skills At University Of Debrecen. *The Annals Of The University Of Oradea. Economic Sciences*. Oradea University Publishing House, Oradea, Romania. ISSN 1222-569X, Eissn 1582-5450
- Fung, H.W., Chau, A.K., Yuan, G.F., Liu, C., & Lam, S.K. (2023). The Nonviolent Communication Behaviors Scale: Cross-Cultural Validity And Association With Trauma And Post-Traumatic Stress. *Research On Social Work Practice*.
- Futurelearn. (2022, July 11). What Is Interpersonal Communication And Why Is It Important? Futurelearn. <https://www.futurelearn.com/info/blog/what-is-interpersonal-communication>
- García, A.N., & Castrillo, P. (2020). "Just Being Us" – Secrecy, Authenticity And Identity In The Americans.
- Gaumer Erickson, A. S., Noonan, P. M., Monroe, K., & McCall, Z. (2021). Assertiveness Formative Questionnaire. In P. Noonan & A. Gaumer Erickson. *The Skills That Matter: Teaching Interpersonal And Intrapersonal Competencies In Any Classroom* (P. 181–182). Corwin.
- Ghufuron, Q.S. (2019). *Communication In Interpersonal Communication*. Researchhub. <https://doi.org/10.496.20583.094>
- Giles, H., Coupland, N., & Coupland, I. U. S. T. I. N. E. (1991). 1. Accommodation Theory: Communication, Context, And Contexts Of Accommodation: Developments In Applied Sociolinguistics, 1.
- Gkonou, C., Mercer, S., And Daubney, M. (2018). Teacher Perspectives On Language Learning Psychology. *Lang. Learn. J.* 46, 501–513. Doi: 10.1080/09571736.2016.1172330
- Grieve, R., Woodley, J., Hunt, S. E., & McKay, A. (2021). Student Fears Of Oral Presentations And Public Speaking In Higher Education: A Qualitative Survey. *Journal Of Further And Higher Education*, 45(9), 1281–1293. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2021.1948509>
- Guba, *The Paradigm Dialog*. SAGE Publications, Incorporated, 1990.
- Gultekin, A., Ozdemir, A. A., & Budak, F. (2018). The Effect Of Assertiveness Education On Communication Skills Given To Nursing Students. *International Journal Of Caring Science*, 11 (1), 395- 401.
- Han, R., & Xu, J. (2020). A Comparative Study Of The Role Of Interpersonal Communication, Traditional Media And Social Media In Pro-Environmental Behavior: A China-Based Study. *International Journal Of Environmental Research And Public Health*, 17(6), 1883. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17061883>
- Henry, A., And Thorsen, C. (2021). Teachers' Self-Disclosures And Influences On Students' Motivation: A Relational Perspective. *Int. J. Biling. Educ. Biling* 24, 1–15. Doi: 10.1080/13670050.2018.1441261
- Heo, J., & Han, S. (2021). The Mediating Effect Of Literacy Of LMS Between Self-Evaluation Online Teaching Effectiveness And Self-Directed Learning Readiness. *Education And Information Technologies*, 26(5), 6097-6108. Available At: <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10639-021-10590-4>.
- Hofstede, G. (1984). *Culture's Consequences: International Differences In Work-Related Values* (Vol. 5). Sage.
- Houser, M. L., & Hosek, A. M. (Eds.). (2018). *Handbook Of Instructional Communication: Rhetorical And Relational Perspectives* (2nd Ed.). Routledge.
- I.Illavarasi, D., & S.No (2024). Enhancing Workplace Productivity: A Review Of Effective Communication Techniques And Their Role In Fostering Team Collaboration And Conflict Resolution. *International Journal For Multidimensional Research Perspectives*.
- Ilie, O. A. (2019, June). The Intercultural Competence. *Developing Effective Intercultural Communication Skills*. In *International Conference Knowledge-Based Organization* (Vol. 25, No. 2, Pp. 264-268).
- Immanuel, E. U. (2019). Initial Development Of Assertive Behavior Inventory. *Practicum Psychologia*, 9(2), 322-338.

- Jacobson, S. K., Morales, N. A., Chen, B., Soodeen, R., Moulton, M. P., & Jain, E. (2019). Love Orloss: Effective Message Framing To Promote Environmental Conservation. *Applied Environmental Education & Communication*, 18, 252–265
- Jalaludin, M., Ihkasan, M. N. (2021) Interpersonal Communication Skills Among The Master’s Students In TVET. *Developing Country Studies Www.iiste.Org ISSN 2224-607X (Paper) ISSN 2225-0565 (Online) Vol.4, No.16, 2021*
- Jalaludin, M.A., & Ihkasan, M.N. (2018). Interpersonal Communication Skills Among The Master’s Students In TVET. *Developing Country Studies*, 4, 110-118.
- Jebbour, M. (2018). University Students’ Perceptions of The Effects of Teacher Selfdisclosure In The English Language Classroom. *J. Eng. Lang. Teach. Linguist.* 3, 275–285. Doi: 10.21462/Jeltl.V3i3.166
- Jebbour, M., And Mouaid, F. (2019). The Impact Of Teacher Self-Disclosure on Student’s Participation In The University English Language Classroom. *Int. J. Learn. High. Educ.* 31, 424–436
- Khuman, P. (2024). THE IMPACT OF NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN TEACHING: ENHANCING EDUCATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS.
- Kiełek-Rataj, E., Wendołowska, A., Kalus, A., & Czyżowska, D. (2020). Openness And Communication Effects On Relationship Satisfaction In Women Experiencing Infertility Or Miscarriage: A Dyadic Approach. *International Journal Of Environmental Research And Public Health*, 17(16), 5721. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17165721>
- Krishna, G. (2023, August 28). Importance Of Interpersonal Skills For Students. *Linkedin.Com*. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-interpersonal-skills-students-dr-p-gnanasundari-krishna>
- Kuper, A., Lingard, L., Levinson, W. (2008). Critically Appraising Qualitative Research. *BMJ*.
- Lauther, A. (2019). Self Control In Interpersonal Communication. *Sagepub*. <https://doi.org/10.4953.50502.49>
- Leisten, L. M., Findling, F., Bellinghausen, J., Kinateder, M., Probst, T., Lion, D., & Shiban, Y. (2021). The Effect Of Nonlexical Verbal Signals On The Perceived Authenticity, Empathy And Understanding Of A Listener. *The European Journal Of Counselling Psychology*, 10(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.46853/001c.27434>
- Lin, S., Fabris, M.A., & Longobardi, C. (2021). Closeness In Student–Teacher Relationships And Students’ Psychological Well-Being: The Mediating Role Of Hope. *Journal Of Emotional And Behavioral Disorders*, 30, 44 - 53.
- Liu, J. (2019). A Counseling Case on Problems Of College Students’ Interpersonal Communication. *International Education Studies*, 12(5), 28. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.V12n5p28>
- Luft, J., & Ingham, H. (1955). The Johari Window, A Graphic Model Of Interpersonal Awareness. *Proceedings of The Western Training Laboratory In Group Development*, 246.
- Ma, J., Li, Q., Ding, W., Wei, X., Liao, H., & Li, Y. (2023). Strategies For College Students To Tell Good Chinese Stories And Show Cultural Confidence Through English Public Speaking Based On “Three-Wide Education” Philosophy. *International Journal Of New Developments In Education*.
- Macintyre, P. D., Gregersen, T., And Mercer, S. (2019). Setting An Agenda For Positive Psychology In SLA: Theory, Practice, And Research. *Modern Lang. J.* 103, 262–274. Doi: 10.1111/Modl.12544
- Mahinay, S. D., Fuentes, J. P., Bernadez, E. G. K., Guanzon, I. M. S., & Cruz, I. D. D. (2024). Readiness Of Fourth Year College Of Education Students For Effective Preservice Teaching In Public Schools. *International Journal Of Research And Innovation In Social Science*, VIII(III), 585–597. <https://doi.org/10.47772/Ijriss.2024.803043>
- Mahmoudi-Dehaki, M., Chalak, A., & Heidari Tabrizi, H. (2021). The Impact Of Learning Through Management Systems Vs. Learning Through Experience Platform On Exam Results Of Digital Natives And Digital Immigrants. *Journal Of Teaching Language Skills*, 40(3), 117- 158. Available At: <https://doi.org/10.22099/Jtls.2021.39227.2922>
- Markevych, Y., Khavanska, A., & Filenko, I. (2022). Improving Students’ Ability To Communicate Interpersonally In English Classroom Discussions Through Group Dynamics Implementation. *JELITA*.
- Masur, P. K. (2018). *Situational Privacy And Self-Disclosure: Communication Processes In Online Environments*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- Mcclaren, D. (2021). *Principles Of Interpersonal Communication*. *Opentextbooklibrary*. <https://doi.org/10.3902.49526.600>
- Mccroskey, J. C. (1977). Oral Communication Apprehension: A Summary Of Recent Theory And Research. *Human Communication Research*, 4(1), 78-96.
- Mehrabian, A. (1967). Inference Of Attitudes From Nonverbal Communication In Two Channels. *Journal Of Consulting Psychology*,

31, 3.

Mehrabian, A. (1969). Some Referents And Measures Of Nonverbal Behavior. *Behav. Res. Methods* 1, 203–207. Doi: 10.3758/BF03208096

Mercer, S., & Dörnyei, Z. (2020). *Engaging Language Learners In Contemporary Classrooms*. Cambridge University Press. *Methods Approaches*.

Min, J.C. (2021). The Relationship between Self-efficacy and Emotional Intelligence (EI) among Tour Guides. *International Journal of Business and Applied Social Science*.

Mock, A., & Hodis, G. M. (2022). Together For Good: Aspects Of Supportive Communication Between Tertiary Classmates That Lead To Academic Success. *Kairaranga*, 23(1), 50-65.

Mutia, E. I., Ridha, M. (2020) Relationship Of Self-Disclosure With Interpersonal Communication Of High School Teenagers. *Jurnal Neo Konseling. Jurnal Neo Konseling*. Volume 1 Number 4 2019. ISSN: Print 2657-0556 – Online 2657-0564. DOI: 10.24036/00184kons2019

Nath, K. (2019). Learner Strategies And Communicative Acquisition: Learner’s Autonomy From The Indian Perspective. *Humanities And Social Sciences Reviews*, 7(6), 1142–1146. <https://doi.org/10.18510/HSSR.2019.76163>

National Univeristy. (2018, October 23). *Interpersonal Communication: Courses With Career Impact*. National University. <https://www.nu.edu/blog/interpersonal-communication/>

Ndiung, S., Menggo, S. (2024) *Problem-Based Learning Analysis In Strengthening College*

Nejad, S.B., Broujeni, A.K., Honarmand, M.M., & Nasab, N.M. (2020). The Effectiveness Of Communication Skills Training On Self-Efficacy And Emotional-Social Adjustment In Women With MS. *Medico-Legal Update*.

Nik-Ahmad-Zuky, N. L., Baharuddin, K. A., & Rahim, A. F. A. (2020). Online Clinical Teaching And Learning For Medical Undergraduates During The COVID-19 Pandemic: The Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM) Experience. *Education In Medicine Journal*, 12(2), 75- 80. Available At: <https://doi.org/10.21315/Eimj2020.12.2.8>

Pace, R. W., & Faules, D. F. (1994). *Organizational Communication*. Eaglewood Cliffs.

Parmaksiz, I. (2019). Assertiveness As The Predictor Of Adjustment To University Life Amongst University Students. *International Journal Of Instruction*, 12(4), 131-148.

Pi, Z., Hong, J., & Hu, W. (2018). Interaction Of The Originality Of Peers’ Ideas And Students’ Openness To Experience In Predicting Creativity In Online Collaborative Groups. *British Journal Of Educational Technology*.

Pishghadam, R., Derakhshan, A., And Zhaleh, K. (2019). The Interplay Of Teacher Success, Credibility, And Stroke With Respect To Students' Willingness To Attend Classes. *Polish Psychol. Bull.* 50, 284–292.

Pishghadam, R., Derakhshan, A., Zhaleh, K., Al-Obaydi L. H. (2021). Students’ Willingness To Attend EFL Classes With Respect To Teachers’ Credibility, Stroke, And Success: A Cross-Cultural Study Of Iranian And Iraqi Students’ Perceptions. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12144-021-01738-Z>

Pozas, M., & Letzel-Alt, V. (2023). Teacher collaboration, inclusive education and differentiated instruction: A matter of exchange, co-construction, or synchronization? *Cogent Education*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2240941>

Przytuła, S., Bruska, A., Szymańska-Czaplak, E., & Tracz-Krupa, K. (2020). Enhancing Cross-Cultural Competence Among Students In An Effort To Fill The Skills Gap In The European Labor Market.

Rabiman, R., Nurtanto, M., & Kholifah, N. (2020). Design And Development E-Learning System By Learning Management System (LMS) In Vocational Education. *Online Submission*, 9(1), 1059-1063.

Ramadona, M., Mamat, W. (2019). The Analysis Of The Impact Of Interpersonal Communication Skills. *Researchhub*. <https://doi.org/10.03953.59692.45>

Rangkuli, T., Regal, D.T., Adams, P. (2020). Environmental Control Effecting Communication Skills And Styles. *Googlescholar*. <https://doi.org/10.3962.49502.34>

Ray, K.L. (2018). *The Impact Of Self-Control On Communication*. Sagepub. <https://doi.org/10.48592.5063.295>

Rido, A. (2020a). English For University Graduate Employability: Students And Employers’ Voices. *Advances In Social Science, Education And Humanities Research*, 430, 6–10. <https://doi.org/10.2991/Assehr.K.200406.002>

Rido, A. (2020b). Why They Act The Way They Do?: Pedagogical Practices Of Experienced Vocational English Language

- Teachers In Indonesia. *International Journal Of Language Education*, 4(2), 24. <https://doi.org/10.26858/Ijole.V4i2.9935>
- Rido, A., Kuswoyo, H., Ayo, R. (2020) Interaction Management Strategies In English Literature Lectures In Indonesian University Setting. *Indonesian Journal Of EFL And Linguistics* vol. 5 No. 2, 2020 eissn: 2503-4197, Pissn: 2527-5070 www.Indonesian-Efl-Journal.Org
- Rini, Y.W., & Anshori, M. (2023). The Role Of Interpersonal Communication In Personal Development And Lifelong Learning For Employees. *Indonesian Journal Of Economic & Management Sciences*.
- Safaei, N., And Shahrokhi, M. (2019). Relationship Between Teacher Self-Disclosure And Teaching Style: Perception Of EFL Teachers. *Cogent Educ.* 6:1678231. Doi: 10.1080/2331186X.2019.1678231
- Samfira, E. M. (2020) Assertive Communication In Universities. *Journal Plus Education*, ISSN:1842-077X, E-ISSN 2068-1151 VOL. XXV. No. 1/2020,361-373
- Saripah, I., Supriatna, M., Oktaviani, B., Solehuddin, M., Suryana, D. (2020) The Profile Of Interpersonal Communication Skills In Elementary School Students. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH VOLUME 9, ISSUE 02, FEBRUARY 2020*. ISSN 2277-8616
- Sarwari A. Q, Wahab. M, Said. M (2022). Factors Influencing Interpersonal Interactions Among Students From Different Nationalities Using English Language As The Primary Means Of Their Daily Communication. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ) Volume 14, Number 1 Ma Pp. 449-45 DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/Awej/Vol14no1.28>*
- Sato, K.J., & Horn, B. (2023). Promoting Higher Order Thinking Skills In A Cross-Cultural Communication Project. *World Journal Of Educational Research*.
- Sherman, S.A., Cameron, C., & Nichols, R. (2023). Promoting Inclusivity In Physical Education And Health With The Theory Of Multiple Intelligences. *Journal Of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 94, 44 - 50.
- Sheybani, M. (2019). The Relationship Between EFL Learners' Willingness To Communicate (WTC) And Their Teacher Immediacy Attributes: A Structural Equation Modelling. *Cogent Psychol.* 6:1607051. Doi: 10.1080/23311908.2019.1607051
- Shim, K. J., Menkhoff, T., Teo, L. Y. Q., & Ong, C. S. Q. (2023). Assessing The Effectiveness Of A Chatbot Workshop As Experiential Teaching And Learning Tool To Engage Undergraduate Students. *Education And Information Technologies*, 1–24. Advance Online Publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10639-023-11795->
- Shoeib, A. F. (2018). Male And Female EFL Teachers' Consciousness Of Self-Disclosure: A Case Study From Al Baha University, Saudia Arabia.
- Silverman, D. (2000). Analyzing Talk And Text. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of Qualitative Research* (2nd Ed.), Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 821–834.
- Singgih, R. (2019). Controlling Emotions During Communication Exchange Through Interpersonal Communication. *Sagepub*. <https://doi.org/10.395.29592.145>
- Sitota, (2018). Assertiveness And Academic Achievement Motivation Of Adolescent Students In Selected Secondary Schools Of Harari Peoples Regional State, Ethiopia. *International Journal Of Education & Literacy Studies*, 6(4), 40-46.
- Skoog, R., Kusumaningsih, S., & Sun, J. (2020). Student Immediacy: The Key to Collaborative Learning Dynamics?.
- Smith, T. (2018). Self Controlling In Interpersonal Communication. *Dreampub*. <https://doi.org/10.485.13045.457>
- Sökmen, Y. (2021). The Role Of Self-Efficacy In The Relationship Between The Learning Environment And Student Engagement. *Educational Studies*, 47(1), 19-37. Students' Interpersonal Communication Skill. *Journal Of Education And Learning (Edulearn) Vol. 18, No. 4, November 2024, Pp. 1350~1361 ISSN: 2089-9823 DOI: 10.11591/Edulearn.V18i4.21219*
- Stringer, H. (2021). Constructive Criticism That Works. <https://www.apa.org>. <https://www.apa.org/monitor/2021/10/career-constructive-criticism>
- Suprayogi, M. (2023). Emotional Intelligence And Interpersonal Communication Among Senior High School Students. DOI:10.1051/E3sconf/202338804046
- Suryawati, C. T. (2018). Teknik Assertive Training Sebagai Usaha Penanganan Masalah Pada Remaja. *Etika Dan Profesi Konselor Di Indonesia*, 63–68.
- Sykownik, P., Maloney, D., Freeman, G., & Masuch, M. (2022). Something Personal From The Metaverse: Goals, Topics, And Contextual Factors Of Self-Disclosure In Commercial Social VR. *Proceedings Of The 2022 CHI Conference On Human Factors In Computing Systems*.

Tamin, N. H., & Mohamad, M. (2020). Google Classroom For Teaching And Learning In Malaysia Primary School During Movement Control Order (MCO) Due To Covid-19 Pandemic: A Literature Review. *International Journal Of Multidisciplinary Research And Publications*, 3(5), 34-37.

Tashakkori, A., & Charles, T. (1998). *Mixes Methodology: Combining Qualitative And Quantitative Approaches*. Applied Social Research Methods Series, 46; Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications Research. BMJ

Trepte, A., Masur, P. K. Scharkow, M. (2018). Mutual Friends' Social Support And Selfdisclosure In Face-To-Face And Instant Messenger Communication. *The Journal Of Social Psychology*, 158(4), 430-445. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.2017.1398707>

Van Der Weiden, A., Benjamins, J., Gillebaart, M., Ybema, J. F., & De Ridder, D. (2020). How To Form Good Habits? A Longitudinal Field Study On The Role Of Self-Control In Habit Formation. *Frontiers In Psychology*, 11, 560.

Varndell W., Elliot D., & Fry M. (2015). Assessing, Monitoring And Managing Continuous Intravenous Sedation For Critically Ill Adult Patients And Implications For Emergency Nursing Practice: A Systematic Literature Review. *Australas Emerg Nurs J*. 2015;18(1):1-23

Varthana. (2024, March 13). College Life: Communication & Interpersonal Skills. Varthana. <https://varthana.com/student/communication-and-interpersonal-skills-in-college-life>

Weber, C., Rehder, M., And Vereenoghe, L. (2021). Student-Reported Classroom Climate Pre And Post Teacher Training In Restorative Practices. *Front. Educ*.6:719357. Doi: 10.3389/Feduc.2021.719357

Wrench, J. S., Punyanunt-Carter, N. M., & Thweatt, A. K. S. (2020). Interpersonal Communication. *Geneseo.Edu*. <https://milnepublishing.geneseo.edu/interpersonalcommunication/chapter/2/>

Yulianti, T., & Sulistyawati, A. (2021). Enhancing Public Speaking Ability Through Focus Group Discussion. *JURNAL PAJAR (Pendidikan Dan Pengajaran)*, 5(2), 287-295.

Zeng, H. L., Chen, D. X., Li, Q., & Wang, X. Y. (2020). Effects Of Seminar Teaching Method Versus Lecture-Based Learning In Medical Education: A Meta-Analysis Of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Medical Teacher*, 42(12), 1343-1349.

Zhang, S., Pan, Y., & Wang, J. Z. (2023). Learning Emotion Representations From Verbal And Nonverbal Communication. In *Proceedings Of The IEEE/CVF Conference On Computer Vision And Pattern Recognition* (Pp. 18993-19004).

Zhang, Y., Ghandour, A., & Shestak, V. (2020). Using Learning Analytics To Predict Students Performance In Moodle LMS. *International Journal Of Emerging Technologies In Learning*, 15(20), 102-115. Available At: <https://doi.org/10.3991/Ijet.V15i20.15915>.

Zheltukhina, M. R., Kislitsyna, N. N., Sergeeva, O. V., Ignateva, R. M., Kosheleva, Y. P., & Lutskovskaia, L. Y. (2023). Adaptation Of Communication Styles Inventory To Russian Context. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 15(4).

Zheltukhina, M.R., Kislitsyna, N.N., Sergeeva, O.V., Ignateva, R.M., Kosheleva, Y.P., & Lutskovskaia, L. (2023). Adaptation Of Communication Styles Inventory To Russian Context. *Contemporary Educational Technology*.

Zheng, J. (2021). A Functional Review Of Research On Clarity, Immediacy, And Credibility Of Teachers And Their Impacts On Motivation And Engagement Of Students. *Front. Psychol*. 12:712419 Doi: 10.3389/Fpsyg.2021.712419

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